

Integrated and harmonized study procedures to assess exposure and early health effects in humans exposed to micro- and nanoplastics: a consensus report from the CUSP Partners

On the behalf of

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GLOSSARY

Additive: A substance intentionally added to a product in small quantities to change or improve the product's performance or enhance its environmental stability.

Adverse outcome pathways (AOPs): conceptual frameworks that outline the sequence of biological events, linking a molecular initiating event (MIE) to an adverse outcome via several key events (KEs). AOPs facilitate the mechanistic understanding of toxicological processes by compiling the existing knowledge in a meaningful manner.

Biodegradation: the process of breaking down into natural materials (carbon dioxide, water, organic matter) when certain physical conditions are met (for example, temperature, humidity, and presence of microorganisms).

Degradation: The process of a material breaking down into smaller pieces through mechanical and/or chemical deterioration.

Hazardous: Involving or exposing one to a risk.

Life-cycle: The MP life cycle includes every stage, from production (primary source), to use and disposal, then transportation through the environment, and final deposition or uptake into the food web. In the case where MP are generated through the degradation of larger plastic pieces (secondary source), the life cycle also includes the transportation of the plastics through the environment, and the degradation of the plastic into MP.

Microplastics (MP): Particles that are greater than 1000 nanometre (nm) and less than 5 millimetres (mm) in their longest dimension and composed of solid polymeric materials to which chemical additives or other substances may have been added. Polymers that are derived in nature that have not been chemically modified (other than by hydrolysis) are excluded.

Nanoplastics (NP): Plastic particles with a size of 1 nm to 1000 nm in length produced by the fragmentation of MP particles.

Plastic: A synthetic material made from a wide range of organic polymers that can be moulded into various solid forms and retain their given shape.

Polymer: A large molecule composed of smaller, repeating, singular molecular units called monomers that are joined chemically through covalent bonds. According to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) a 'polymer' means a substance consisting of molecules characterized by the sequence of one or more types of monomer units and comprising a simple weight majority of molecules containing at least three monomer units which are covalently bound to at least one other monomer unit or other reactant and consists of less than a simple weight majority of molecules of the same molecular weight.

Primary microplastics: Microplastics that are intended for use in the current form (for example, plastic pellets and beads in personal care products).

Secondary microplastics: Particles that result from the environmental degradation (breakdown) of larger plastics items (i.e., due to mechanical forces and/or weathering conditions).

ABBREVIATIONS

8OHdG	8-Oxo-2'-deoxyguanosine
8OHG	8-Hydroxy-guanosine
ATR-FTIR	Attenuated Total Reflection- Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy
ATS	American Thoracic Society
CC16	Clara cell 16kD protein
CRM	Confocal Raman Microscopy
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EA	Exhaled Air
EBC	Exhaled Breath Condensate
eCRF	electronic case report form
EIA	Enzyme immunoassay
ELISA	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay
ENM	Engineered nanomaterial
ERS	European Respiratory Society
FEF	Forced expiratory flow
FEV ₁	Forced expiratory volume in the first second
FVC	Forced vital capacity
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
GSD	Geometric standard deviation
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
hs-CRP	High-sensitivity C-reactive protein
ICP-MS	Inductively-coupled plasma with mass spectrometry
IgE	Immunoglobulin E (antibodys)
IL	Interleukin
ISAAC	International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood
LC-MS	Liquid chromatography with mass spectrometry
LDSA	Lung deposited surface area
LTB ₄	Leukotriene B ₄
MDA	Malondialdehyde
miRNA	microRNA
MN	Micronucleus
MNPs	Micro- and nanoplastics
MNRET	Micronucleated reticulocyte
NTA	Nanoparticle tracking analysis
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
OPC	Optical Particle Counter
PA	Polyamide
PAN	Polyacrylonitrile
PE	Polyethylene
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PMMA	Polymethyl methacrylate
PP	Polypropylene
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride

PBMC	Peripheral blood mononuclear cells
RA	Risk Assessment
REDCap	Research electronic data capture
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
RT-PCR	Real-time polymerase chain reaction
SPT	Skin prick test
TAC	Total antioxidant capacity
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
TBARS	Thiobarbituric acid reactive substances
TNF	Tumor Necrosis Factor
TURBO-DECCS	Transportable unit for the research on biomarkers obtained from disposable exhaled condensate collections systems

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Plastics are defined by the International Organisation for Standardisation (International Organization for Standardization, 2020), as macromolecules that are made of repetitive units (monomers), which are mainly composed of carbon and hydrogen atoms. To increase the technical properties of basic polymers, a wide variety of additives and plasticizers are used, with the result of enhancing their mechanical, physical, and chemical properties for specific applications. As a result, plastics are – and should be regarded as - complex mixtures which encompass a wide range of materials with different properties, environmental and biological behaviour, as well as different ways to interact with biological systems, thus leading to potential adverse effects.

Considering the life-cycle of plastics released into the environment, they can undergo ageing processes till their biodegradation. These natural processes can dramatically change their physicochemical properties, especially following their breaking down into smaller particles.

Plastic materials found in environmental media have been classified according to their size, in microplastics (MPs, 1 μm – 5 mm) and nanoplastics (NPs, < 1 μm). According to the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), the terms MPs and NPs are applied for “*any solid-polymer-containing particles, to which additives or other substances may have been added, and where $\geq 1\%$ w/w of particles have all dimensions between 1 nm and 5 mm or for fibres, a length between 3 nm - 15 mm and a length-to-diameter ratio > 3*” (European Chemical Agency, 2023). Depending on their origin, they can reach the environment as primary micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) (i.e., fabric fibres, pellets, or virgin plastics included in personal care product formulations that are released directly), as well as secondary MNPs, which are produced incidentally, via fragmentation of larger plastic items

The European Observatory for Nanomaterials (EUON) pointed out that “*nanoplastics have not been as strictly defined as engineered nanomaterials, as these latter are already covered by different regulatory frameworks. The majority of nanoplastics in the environment is actually of secondary origin. This means that they are formed via a fragmentation process from larger plastic items that have been released unintentionally into the environment*” (A. J. Kokalj & Kühnel, 2021). Thus, in spite of their similarities with nanomaterials, NPs are materials, characterized by multiple random polymer types of different shapes and sizes and a wide range of surface properties that are governed mainly by their higher heterogeneity, including hundreds of thousands of contaminants that are adsorbed onto the plastic surfaces (Wieland et al., 2024). As soon as a plastic particle enters the environment it gets coated by various biomolecules forming a so-called eco-corona (Ramsperger et al., 2020; Wieland et al., 2024). This eco-corona has a great relevance in determining the interactions with biological systems behind the size matter (Wieland et al., 2024). In addition, the polymeric matrix may include, i.e., metal ions, polysaccharides, natural organic matter, Fe-Mn hydroxides, dust, pathogens (Gigault et al., 2021; Ter Halle et al., 2017), which can affect the potential adverse effects by MNPs *per se*.

1.2 MNPs in the indoor environments: occurrence and emission sources

To date, there is no doubt of the presence of MNPs in indoor air. (Wieland et al., 2022) estimated that humans might inhale on average > 48,000 MP particles per day. The abundance of MNPs in indoor

environments is likely influenced by the use of plastics in diverse human activities. Flooring, synthetic garments, textile and household furniture seem to be the significant determinants for MNPs contamination of the air as reviewed by Facciola and co-workers (Facciola et al., 2021). The highest concentrations of indoor airborne MPs (1600 ± 1200 MPs/m³) were reported by Liao and co-workers (Liao et al., 2021) using active air filtering. They reported that 2/3 of the number of all particles collected were smaller than 30 μ m (Liao et al., 2021). Therefore, we can speculate that smaller particles dominate airborne MPs, which is plausible considering that smaller particles remain suspended in the air longer than larger particles. However, to date, there are no data on the occurrence and prevalence of MPs smaller than 5 μ m in private indoor environments [*NB: this can be due to a limitation of commonly used methods to characterize MNPs*]. Therefore, reliable statements regarding the potential exposure to very small MPs or NPs cannot be made.

Plastic resin pellets are industrial feedstock for plastic products. They are typically spherical or cylindrical and only a few millimetres in diameter. In addition, plastic microbeads are used in many industrial applications, i.e., as ingredients in printer inks, spray paints, injection moldings and abrasives. Thus, a proportion of the microplastics used in industrial applications will escape from production sites and enter the environment. In some working environments, the potential of being exposed to MNPs, generated during mechanical and environmental degradation of plastic goods or by MNP being added as ingredients may be enhanced (Murata et al., 2020). Even though the US National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) is actively studying specific industrial applications and processes where there is a potential for exposure to plastic particles, their hazards, and tools to minimize exposures, to date, the occurrence and the emission sources of MNPs at workplaces has received poor attention (Marasco et al., 2021; Ramsperger et al., 2023). Wieland and co-workers (Wieland et al., 2022) compared workplace concentrations of different airborne microparticles and their associated occupational diseases. As for many particles and fibers, the physicochemical properties like size, shape, ζ -potential, adsorbed molecules and pathogens, and the MP's bio-persistence should be regarded as possible drivers of MP toxicity (Murashov et al., 2020; Wieland et al., 2022).

In the workplace, besides the dynamic of release, especially after thermal degradation of polymers, airborne nanoplastics have been poorly characterized, due to the complexity of their chemical compositions, size, shape and their association with other chemicals.

Few studies have provided a quantification of the release and the potential for exposure, but it has been simulated. Zimmer and Maynard (Zimmer & Maynard, 2002) have assessed the number and size of particles emitted during mechanical degradation of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE); as revealed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis, the aerosol was composed by a large number of single particles (8.0×10^4) around 10–20 nm in diameter. Similarly, environmental degradation of plastic goods can lead to potential exposures to MNPs among workers in the waste management and recycling operations (Wohlleben et al., 2013). Degradation of carpets and other synthetic products can generate airborne fibers falling under the definition of MNPs, with potential for exposure among office workers and custodial staff.

Another example of a workplace process potentially leading to worker exposure is machining of polymer and plastic products generating dusts (Dris et al., 2017). In this study, the ubiquity of the fibres was highlighted not only in outdoors air but also in two private apartments and an office, the

indoor concentration being significantly higher (1.0 to 60 fibres/m³) than outdoors (from 0.3 to 1.5 fibres/m³), with 33% of them composed of polypropylene (PP).

In the bottom-up mechanism of production, MNPs can be emitted during high energy or high heat processes (such as laser cutting or high-speed drilling) during treatment of polymer composites such as carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) (Walter et al., 2016). The emission characterization has been performed for different laser processes and laser systems, simulating possible release dynamics occurring at the workplace. While the largest number of particles found were in the range of an aerodynamic diameter near 100 nm, the majority of the particle mass was represented by relatively few large particles with an aerodynamic diameter of more than 6.6 µm (Walter et al., 2016).

3D printing is becoming popular not only in offices but also at home. It works by depositing molten plastic layer upon layer at temperatures up to 320 °C and then extrudes it onto a moving baseplate to produce different objects, including toys, guns, and artificial limbs. The higher the temperature, the more gases are produced, and more particles ultimately form. Although many basic questions about the amounts and types of compounds in 3D printer emissions have still to be answered, workers in factories hosting plastic processors and 3D printing from melting or fusing of plastics can be exposed to airborne nano- and microplastic particles (Stefaniak, Bowers, et al., 2019; Stefaniak et al., 2018; Stefaniak, Johnson, et al., 2019). Thus, even though no systematic measurements have been carried out, by continuously melting through the extruder nozzle, 3D printing releases potentially harmful volatile organic compounds and ultrafine particles (UFPs) into the air. For instance, printing with acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) gives off styrene and formaldehyde, nylon releases caprolactam, a respiratory irritant and polylactic acid (PLA) emits methyl methacrylate, a mild skin irritant.

1.3 Presence of MNPs in human tissue and knowledge about health effects

To date, MNPs occurrence and recognition in human tissues and fluids has been poorly investigated. Epidemiological studies following a proper design have never been carried out and, to date, only small case-study reports are available. This fact is likely affected by the lack of reliable analytical methods, which allow the detection of MNPs in biological samples as well as by the lack of standardized protocols for collection, identification, and analytical quantification even at low levels. All these features explain the difficulty to obtain a real estimation of the internal dose of MPs and NPs in the human body.

Schwabe and co-workers (Schwabl et al., 2019) quantified MPs in human stool samples from 8 residents in Europe and Asia (with different dietary patterns), demonstrating the presence of 20 pieces of MPs - sized 50-500 µm and mainly PP (62.8%) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET; 17%) - per 10 g of stool related to food consumption. Subsequent studies used human stool specimens to provide the magnitude of human exposure through food and beverages intake. Zhang and co-workers (J. Zhang et al., 2021) demonstrated 10 times higher concentrations of PET and polycarbonate (PC) in infant faeces than adult samples due to the extensive use of plastics articles (i.e., baby feeding bottles, sippy cups) and clothing, and the MPs released from packaged plastic containers used for processed baby foods (J. Zhang et al., 2021). Associations between packaged water and beverages consumption and MPs abundance (PP, PET, and polystyrene, PS, polymers) in faeces were assessed in 23 healthy students living in the urban city of Beijing (China) (N. Zhang et al., 2021). An average concentration

of 9.159 µg/g of high-density polyethylene (HPDE) and 9.885 µg/g of PS in human stool from a fisherman community (Luqman et al., 2021), as well as an average concentration of 10.19 µg/g of PP in human stool from a farming community were reported (Wibowo et al., 2021). High faecal levels of PET (34.0%) were found in patients with inflammatory bowel disease as compared to healthy (22.3%) subjects, confirming that some diseases can exacerbate the retention of MNPs arising from plastic packaging (Yan et al., 2022).

Studies on different kinds of human specimens, i.e., breastmilk, placenta, saliva, head hair, blood, and urine, have provided evidence of plastic burden in the human body. The occurrence of PP particles (ranging from 5 to 10 µm in size) in human placenta and polyethylene (PE), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), and PP (ranging from 2 to 12 µm) in human breastmilk, highlights the transgenerational potential health effects of these pollutants (Ragusa et al., 2021, 2022). Although not accessible for biomonitoring purposes, the human placenta can accumulate both PE, PP, and PS with sizes >50 µm (Braun et al., 2021). A very recent study of Campen and co-workers (Campen et al., 2024) demonstrate that MNPs are selectively accumulated into the human brain and concentrations are rising over time.

These particles could reach organs via the bloodstream, since the plastic particles detected in blood are likely to be internalized by crossing the mucosa. In a recent investigation, PET, PE and polymers of styrene (a sum parameter of PS, expanded PS, acetonitrile butadiene styrene etc.), at a size range between 0.7-500 µm, were found in the blood of 22 healthy individuals by Leslie and co-workers (Leslie et al., 2022), although accidental contamination and other critical analytical issues of the used protocol cannot be ruled out (Kuhlman, 2022). The presence of MPs in urine samples of six volunteers from different cities in the south of Italy was recently investigated and fragments (average size: 4-15 µm) were found (Pironti et al., 2022).

It is recognized that following inhalation of thermal breakdown products of PTFE, mild to severe pulmonary dysfunction known as "polymer fume fever" can develop (Sprout, 1988; Williams, 1974). This disturbance has been associated with the presence of nanoscale particles within the decomposition products - including polymers - in fumes, capable of reaching the respiratory exchange zone and the lung interstitium.

Historical epidemiological studies indicated a causal relationship between the occupational exposure to high concentrations of nylon fibres and flocks (Eschenbacher et al., 1999; Kern et al., 1998), synthetic textile fibres (Gallagher et al., 2015; Mastrangelo et al., 2003), or PVC dust (Carrasco et al., 1980; Girardi et al., 2022; Lawin et al., 2015; Mastrangelo et al., 2003; Studnicka et al., 1995) and the development of lung diseases, including pulmonary inflammation, fibrosis and even cancer. However, the majority of the studies conducted more recently have focused on evaluating the exposure of workers to MNPs, without assessing the health outcomes (Zuri et al., 2023). Therefore, most of the knowledge on the potential toxic effects of MNPs rely on the scarce *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies conducted so far. Although they are valuable sources of information, these studies cannot capture the complexity of human exposures in terms of duration (i.e., whole working life) or combined effects. In addition to the particulate material, potentially hazardous chemicals used as plastic additives (i.e., plasticizers, flame retardants, stabilisers etc) or non-intentionally added substances may leach during handling of the plastic products and waste (Horodytska et al., 2020).

Furthermore, plastic particles can act as carriers of other environmental pollutants (i.e., polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons) or pathogens into the human body (Prata et al., 2020; Shi et al., 2023).

1.4 Rationale for human biomonitoring in MNP exposure and risk assessment

Humans are exposed to MNPs mainly through inhalation and ingestion (Ageel et al., 2022; Barceló et al., 2023), although certain evidence shows that the dermal route of exposure via cosmetics and personal care products might contribute to the total load of MNPs in the human body (Enyoh et al., 2020). The presence of MNPs has been demonstrated in different human tissues, such as lungs, blood, sputum, testis or placenta, among others (see reviews of Barceló et al., 2023; Kutralam-Muniasamy et al., 2023; Thompson et al., 2024; Zuri et al., 2023). However, the capacity of MNPs to exert toxic effects will depend on their hazardous nature, and the accumulated concentration and lifetime in the tissues (P. Wu et al., 2022), which are influenced not only by the polymer composition, but also by the size, shape and surface properties of the MNPs (Xu et al., 2022). Unfortunately, there are currently no studies available on human biokinetics of MNPs.

Due to their small size, micro- and nano-plastics can interact with biological systems and represent a possible factor affecting health in exposed people, with demonstrated ability to cause functional changes in the target organs (primarily the lung and the gastrointestinal system), oxidative stress (OS) and activation of inflammatory pathways (Dick Vethaak & Legler, 2021; Panizzolo et al., 2023).

In most health risk assessment frameworks for chemicals, the default approach for exposure assessment is to integrate external measurements with estimates of intake from different sources and different routes of exposure. In spite of the uncertainties associated with this approach, having access to data on the internal exposure generated by human biomonitoring (HBM) gives a more complete picture of human exposure and can be used to improve chemical risk assessment (RA) by providing information on actual human exposure via multiple exposure pathways. HBM is a recognized and important tool for assessing the internal exposure of humans resulting from aggregated exposure to chemicals and inclusion of HBM data could improve RA for the general population and workers (OECD, 2022).

For instance, **POLYRISK** has developed a modular RA framework for MNPs, focusing primarily on inhalation as a key exposure route for humans that combines several integrated approaches to testing and assessment (IATAs). The framework starts with basic physicochemical characterisation (step 1), followed by assessing the potential for inhalation exposure (step 2) and includes several modules for toxicological assessment (step 3) (Vogel et al., 2024).

HBM is thus complementary to exposure assessment and consists of measuring a chemical/material or a biomarker in biological fluids at the level of a subject or a group of subjects exposed by different routes including inhalation, oral and dermal routes. Biomarkers are substances or their metabolites, or products of an interaction between a substance and some target molecule that are measurable in a human body compartment. An exposure biomarker is the concentration of a parent compound or its metabolites in biological matrices, whereas an effect biomarker is a measurable biochemical, physiological, and behavioural effects or other alterations within an organism that, depending on the magnitude, can be associated with an established or possible health impairment or disease (Zare Jeddi et al., 2021). In the case of MNPs – like as for substances that not undergo metabolism - tracking particles in biological matrices should ideally be informative in terms of internal dose. However,

such characterization is very challenging and the few available studies show no comparable results, due to the lack of validated and harmonized methods (Thompson et al., 2024).

Since effect biomarkers often reflect subclinical changes before the onset of disease, they are a valuable tool for anticipating the potential adverse effects of new and emerging chemicals and elucidating dose–effect relationships. Some effect biomarkers can provide a high degree of confidence in predicting the potential for adverse effects in a population based on marker levels because the causal relationship of biological events between the marker and the adverse outcome is sufficiently understood (i.e., genotoxic effects as early biomarkers of carcinogenicity). Other biomarkers provide more limited indications of the potential for adverse effects because the link between the marker and the adverse outcome is less well known. That is, i.e., the case of biomarkers of oxidative stress, as high levels of these biomarkers have been associated with a variety of adverse outcomes (US Environmental Protection Agency, 2025).

In occupational population studies, effect biomarkers can help in supporting regulatory decisions by increasing the weight of evidence for a given or mixed chemical exposures. In clinical studies, biomarkers offer the opportunity to provide scientific confirmation of proposed exposure-disease pathways in patient populations (Ladeira, 2024). However, evidence on the adverse health effects related to of MNP exposure in human populations is even sparser than that on internal MNP exposure levels (Zuri et al., 2023).

Biomarkers can reveal changes in biological systems resulting from complex pathways of exposure. With the identification of such biological endpoints, representing the key initiating events towards adaptive or adverse outcomes, it should be feasible to envisage a panel of surrogate biomarkers to be applied and validated, especially in occupational settings, where exposure may occur and can be more easily characterized.

Therefore, human biomonitoring studies assessing exposure and effect biomarkers from the same populations are needed to support a consistent RA towards several classes of foreign chemicals and materials, including MNPs.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE EXPOSURE MONITORING AND HUMAN BIOMONITORING CAMPAIGNS IN OCCUPATIONAL SETTINGS

The general **objective of a stationary monitoring campaigns** is to define the potential for exposure to MNPs in the selected areas of activity, obtaining quantitative data related to the levels of exposure to MNPs and, when possible, correlating them to information gathered in biomonitoring campaigns performed in parallel. For a detailed characterization of the scenarios in which the release of MNPs occurs and / or workers are exposed to them, a methodology has to be followed in stages, applying the classical tools of Industrial Hygiene implemented with high-precision equipment. The resulting output that a monitoring campaign should be the following:

- Characterization of MNPs emission in the most representative production areas.
- Determination of the potential exposure to MNPs during different processes, including quantitative data related to the levels of exposure of a particulate matter in a range of 10 nm to 10 µm; therefore, in the inhalable and respirable ranges.
- Determination of the spatial variability of MNPs in the air.

- Determination of the physicochemical properties (i.e., size, shape, polymer type, etc) of MNPs.
- A detailed report for the company with the obtained results.

Provided that exposure assessment has found a measurable amount of MNPs in the air or from other sources, then biomonitoring studies can be consistently carried out.

The **objective of the human biomonitoring** campaign is, in general, to investigate whether MNPs emissions may impact human health by measuring biomarkers of exposure and of early health effects in workers occupationally exposed in selected exposure scenarios or in the general population. More specifically, the objectives can be summarized as follows: i) Assessment of the inhaled dose (focus on exposure by inhalation in the cases of occupationally exposed populations) and absorbed dose; ii) Application of a panel of biomarkers investigating (pro-)inflammatory and genotoxic effects, and oxidative stress at local (lung) and systemic level as a result of a given exposure pattern; iii) To understand the health relevance of eventual changes in lung biopathology and systemic biochemical changes; iv) To validate a set of biomarkers to be applied for long-term health assessment of groups at risk. However, in the new field we are facing, biomonitoring can have complementary goals, affected by the final output. For instance, in its biomonitoring study, **ImpTox** has focused on the effects of MNPs combined with contaminants to evaluate whether ingested and inhaled MNPs augments allergic disease.

For this reason, we recommend performing exposure assessment and biomonitoring campaigns in parallel to, when possible, correlate the results. The comparison of exposure levels with biological endpoints should enable to evaluate the effective dose of particles and associated chemicals that is taken up by the body considering all exposure routes, inter-individual variability in terms of uptake, metabolism and excretion, as well as the efficiency of protection equipment, if any.

3. STUDY DESIGN

3.1 General framework

In epidemiologic studies, comparisons of an outcome incidence or prevalence are made across subgroups defined by exposure. There are several types of epidemiologic studies.

In a **cohort study** the study population that is free of a specific outcome is sampled from the source population and is followed multiple times over time until the outcome is developed.

Panel studies are short-term cohort studies aiming at studying short-term health effects or biomarkers of effect. As each subject serves as his own control, individual risk factors are especially well-controlled. As in a cohort study, in a panel study the study population is also followed multiple times over time. The distinction between a cohort study is that at study entry, the study population is a cross-sectional sample of the source population and is not required to be free of a specific outcome. Panel study populations are usually characterized by relatively small size and detailed exposure assessment.

Longitudinal studies which have multiple observations over time (cohort and panel studies) have the advantage that temporal order of events can be observed making them the most suitable for the identification of cause-effect relationships. These types of study can be used to investigate the

incidence of a condition. Another advantage is the possibility to document exposure before the outcome has developed, minimizing recall bias. On the down side, longitudinal studies - and especially cohort studies - are time consuming and costly.

In contrast to longitudinal studies, **cross-sectional studies** sample the study population from the source population always including those who have the disease at one point in time, resulting in the prevalence of an outcome. To date, the health effects of MNPs have been approached by this design, which seems appropriate to assess possible associations in well characterized groups to be confirmed in larger populations.

In a **case-control study**, case and control subjects are sampled from a source population, which represents a hypothetical study population. With regard to their possible past exposure to the risk being studied, subjects who do have a medical condition (cases) are compared with subjects who don't have this medical condition (controls). In contrast to the study types described above, a case-control study cannot provide information on the absolute risk of the disease (incidence or prevalence), but only a relative risk estimate. A case-control study may be nested in a cohort or panel study to investigate exposures or other potential parameters that were not documented at study entry. However, implementing case-control studies implies that health end-points have already been identified, which is not yet the case for MNPs.

An advantage of the case-control design is a greater statistical power, given the fact that statistical power for longitudinal studies require a sufficient number of incident cases to appear while cross-sectional studies need a random sample large enough for a sufficient number of prevalent cases.

Both cross-sectional and case-control studies tend to be less costly to carry out than longitudinal studies, as well as having the potential to be shorter in duration. A possible limitation is not being able to observe the temporal order of effects. Since the exposure assessment in these study types is done after the outcome has developed, "recall bias" may occur. This may be more problematic in case of chronic effects for which cumulative exposure over a longer duration has to be assessed.

3.2 Specific approaches carried out to date by the CUSP Partners

Human studies have been performed by all the five projects included within the CUSP cluster. However, each project has used a different and specific approach, which are summarized in **Table 1**. The approaches have focused on the general populations (marked in blue at **Table 1**) or on occupationally exposed populations (marked in orange in **Table 1**).

AURORA has focused on better understanding MNP exposures and toxicological and health effects on reproductive and early-life health. MNPs and MNP-associated chemicals (i.e., additives) are measured in tissues relevant for early-life development (placenta, cord blood, amniotic fluid, meconium, foetal tissue). This will be combined with epidemiological investigations to provide the first extensive evaluation of maternal and foetal MNP exposures and health perturbations, including placental function, immune-inflammatory responses, oxidative stress, accelerated aging, endocrine disruption, and child development.

Table 1. Study approaches used in each of the five EU projects integrated into the CUSP cluster

PROJECT	APPROACH
	Studies evaluating the impact of MNP exposure on early life (mother-newborn) , and on women of reproductive age .
	Cross-sectional study involving schoolchildren (aged 6-18 years) to assess the impact of ingested and inhaled MNPs on allergic diseases
	Two occupational health studies investigating the impact of inhaled MNPs on workers of textile and plastic recycling industries . One study on chronic kidney disease patients in pre-dialysis stage with assumed reduced clearance of MNPs from the body.
	Two occupational health studies investigating the impact of inhaled MNPs on workers involved in 3D printing processes and in molding technopolymers .
	Two studies investigating MNP exposure in real-life settings: football players (rubber granulate-infilled field) and traffic-exposed groups . One occupational health study investigating the impact of inhaled MNPs on workers of textile industry .

The **ImpTox** study is a cross-sectional study, involving schoolchildren (aged 6-18 years) from 3 distinct microgeographical regions in Croatia, presumably differing in the levels of exposure to MNP. Children have been recruited in primary and secondary schools in 2 continental regions in Croatia (Zagreb, the capital city and its surroundings and the Eastern regions of Slavonia) and the Mediterranean regions of Dalmatia. Prior to any procedures, participants (and their parents/caregivers) will need to sign an informed consent for participation in the study. All children will undergo a skin prick test (SPT) to a standard palette of inhaled allergens and common food allergens and they (their parents/caregivers) will be asked to fill out questionnaires on their personal and family history of allergy, dietary and lifestyle habits as well as consumer awareness and perception of MNPs. Blood (serum) samples will be taken, as well as stool samples at the time of recruitment and approximately 6 months after.

PlasticHeal has assessed the exposure and health effects of inhaled MNPs in two occupational scenarios: workers of the fabric manufacturing industry and workers of the recycling industry. In both cases, the levels of exposure and effect biomarkers of workers are compared to those of control groups, who are not exposed to MNPs at their working environments. In addition, **PlasticHeal** has also investigated the potential higher internal exposure and associated immune effects in chronic kidney disease patients in a pre-dialysis stage (before starting dialysis) in comparison to matched control individuals. Patients are assumed to have higher internal concentration of MNPs due to their limited capacity for clearing them from the body, and can therefore be considered as a high-risk population group.

PlasticsFate carried out two small rather explorative biomonitoring studies, involving two different types of work environments. The first campaign was carried out in the laboratories of the University of Pavia that were involved in 3D printing processes. The second took place at a company specialised in printing of products with specific aesthetic and technical characteristics, using both technopolymers and high-performance polymers, within the more articulated electrical and automotive sectors. The rationale for these biomonitoring studies was to assess the feasibility of the application of a study protocol in an occupational setting.

In the **POLYRISK** project, there have been performed three human studies to investigate exposure to MNPs in both occupational and real-life settings. The football field study in Norway is comparing exposure to MNPs in players playing either on an artificial football field with rubber granulates or with crushed olivestones as infill. In the traffic study in the Netherlands, exposure to MNPs from the traffic was studied in 3 different setting (highway, stop and go location, and an urban parc location). In the textile factory study in Romania, exposure to MNPs was studied in a factory setting. In all studies, both air and biological samples were collected to better understand the relationship between external and internal exposure. In all studies effects on the immune system were studied by immune cell profiling by using specialised flow cytometry approaches

4. TARGET POPULATION, ELIGIBILITY AND RECRUITMENT STRATEGY

4.1 Target population

As MNPs are ubiquitous environmental pollutants, the target population can vary according to the aim of the study, as well as the specificity and sensitivity of biomarkers, able to detect subtle changes linked to such exposure. It is likely that workers can experience higher levels of exposure as compared to the “general population”. However, it should be taken into account that any occupational exposure could simply overlap with the background, thus making any effect attributable to MNPs indistinguishable from that expected from other pollutants. Ideally, also for ethical reasons (ability to give an informed consent) the studied population should consist of healthy subjects aged 18-65 years, both men and women, occupationally exposed. Preliminary assessment based on site visits and specific should allow to evaluate the likelihood of exposure to MNPs (i.e., in FFF 3D printers, Plastic production, Plastic recycling... etc).

In occupational studies, a reference/control group should be recruited, possibly outside the studied company. The controls should be as much as possible matched with the exposed subjects in terms of sex, age and tobacco smoking status, plus any other variable affecting MNPs exposure.

Considering studies involving specific subgroups or susceptible groups of the general population, i.e., **ImpTox** clinical study involved a pediatric population cohort (aged 6-18 years), based on predicted differential exposure to MNPs and other environmental and lifestyle factors, as well as susceptibility to allergy (allergic vs. healthy subjects). Subjects have been recruited from three distinct and different geographical regions in Croatia: 2 continental regions (Zagreb, highly urban) and Slavonia (urban and rural) and 1 Mediterranean region (urban and rural population), differing in the levels of environmental exposure, lifestyle and nutrition habits, as well as different environmental protection measures and human activities. Different geographical regions will allow for underpinning differences not only in dietary behaviour but also in environmental levels of MNPs in different sources (food, water, other routes of exposure), in rural vs. urbanised areas. In **AURORA**, newborns from existing bird cohorts have been approached. In addition, a proof-of-concept study, termed the **AURORA** Household Plastics Study, was performed to evaluate MNP exposure and the determinants in women of reproductive age. Around 100 women aged 18-45 years residing within 70 kilometers of UMC Utrecht were recruited within the Utrecht University network or social media.

In the 3 human studies in the **POLYRISK** project both the general population and an occupational population were studied. In the Norwegian football field study, players participated in matches on two indoor fields – one with rubber granulate infill and another with olive sand, a mixture of crushed

olive pits and sand. In the traffic study volunteers performed physical activity at three locations: a highway, a stop-and-go area, and an urban background site. In the textile study, MNP exposure was evaluated for factory workers involved in the production of various fibre types for textiles.

Finally, **PlasticsFate** and **PlasticHeal** have also focused on occupational exposed populations. The former has approached workers related to 3D printing technologies using thermoplastic filaments, whereas the latter has approached workers of the fabric manufacturing and recycling sectors. In addition, **PlasticHeal** has also assessed MNP exposure in chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients at pre-dialysis stage, whose particle clearance from the body may be compromised.

Table 2 provides a more detailed explanation of the different human studies performed by each project. The studies have been classified as approaching workers occupationally exposed, adult individuals of the general population, or sub-groups of the general population at high-risk.

4.2 Eligible/Inclusion and exclusion criteria

In general, volunteers should be recruited provided they are able to give informed consent, and have sufficient knowledge of any of the national languages or English.

Inclusion criteria should include targeted questions. For instance, in **ImpTox**, the inclusion criteria were the proven sensitization to at least one (food) allergen, preferably but not limited to seafood and/or diagnosis of an allergic disease (asthma, allergic rhinitis, atopic dermatitis and food allergy) and matching non-allergic controls. i) Asthma- Participants with a clinical diagnosis of asthma (according to ERS/ATS guidelines) (Gaillard et al., 2021) for at least one year, being on a stable dose of anti-inflammatory treatment for at least one month with partially controlled or uncontrolled asthma according to GINA guidelines (Global Initiative for Asthma. Global Strategy for Asthma Management and Prevention, www.ginaasthma.org) or and according to the ISAAC (International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood) criteria were recruited; ii) Allergic rhinitis/rhinoconjunctivitis- Participants with clinical diagnosis of allergic rhinitis for at least 1 year with symptoms of the nose, induced after exposure to allergens via IgE-mediated hypersensitivity reactions (symptoms of watery rhinorrhea, nasal obstruction, nasal itching and sneezing), according to the EUFOREA (European Forum for Research and Education in Allergy and Airway Diseases) classification, and according to the ISAAC criteria were recruited. Atopic dermatitis- based on historical features, morphology and distribution of skin lesions, and associated clinical signs (according to the criteria of American Academy of Dermatology, (Chu et al., 2024) and classified by ISAAC criteria; iii) Food allergy- according to the European Academy of Allergy and Clinical Immunology (EAACI) guidelines (Santos et al., 2023) and using medical history confirmed by a significantly positive sIgE or SPT to food.

Exclusion criteria: known inborn or perinatal pulmonary disease; pulmonary malformation; oxygen therapy after birth with a duration of more than 24 h; ventilator support or mechanical ventilation after birth; diagnosis of cystic fibrosis; primary ciliary dyskinesia; heart failure diagnosed after birth affecting pulmonary circulation; major respiratory diseases such as i.e., interstitial lung disease. Moreover, children are excluded from study visits and biomaterial collection in the case of fever of at least 38.5 °C during the last two weeks prior to the planned visit.

Table 2. Detailed explanation of the human studies performed by each CUSP project according to the approached population.

Project	Groups	Exposure assessment	Biomarkers of exposure	Effect biomarkers
OCCUPATIONALLY EXPOSED POPULATIONS				
plasticheal	Fibre manufacturing workers (N = 29) Recycling workers (N = 17) Controls (N = 29)	Life style habits (questionnaire) Exposure measures (air)	Microplastics (FTIR) (EBC, blood & urine) Nanoplastics (CRM) (EBC, blood & urine) Additives & contaminants (urine)	Inflammation (blood) Genotoxicity (buccal cells & blood) Changes in microbiota (stool)
PlasticsFatE	3D printing research laboratories (5 technicians + 5 controls; at beginning & end of working week) Molding technopolymers (23 workers)	Exposure measures (air) Questionnaire on life style, health status and confounding variables	Number and size of particles (Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis) (EBC) Additives - phthalates metabolomics (urine)	Inflammation and oxidative stress (EBC) Inflammation and endothelial activation (blood) Antioxidant capacity (blood and urine) DNA oxidized bases (urine) Proteomic and metabolomics (urine)
POLYRISK	Textile workers (N = 35) Controls (N = 11)	Exposure measures (air)	Micro- and nanoplastics as polymers (Pyrolysis GCMS) (blood)	Immune cell profiling (blood)
GENERAL POPULATION				
AURORA	Women of reproductive age (18-45, N=100) (panel study)	Household dust	Micro- and nanoplastic polymers (blood, urine)	Not assessed
POLYRISK	Young athletes playing on a football field with rubber granulates (N=36) Players were their own controls (after playing on a field with olivestone field infill)	Air sampling (SEM+RAMAN, pyrolysis GCMS, weight, volatile organic compounds)	Micro- and nanoplastics as rubber polymers (Pyrolysis GCMS) (blood) Selected metabolites (urine)	Single cell Immune cell profiling (CyTOF) (blood) Inflammation (OLINK) (blood)
POLYRISK	Traffic participants cycling near a highway in an urban parc or by a stop/go location (N=23)	Air sampling (rubber with pyrolysis GCMS, metals, organic compounds)	Micro- and nanoplastics as rubber polymers (blood)	Immune cell profiling (blood) Inflammation (blood) Hematology Lung function
HIGH-RISK POPULATIONS				
AURORA	Newborns (n=800) from existing birth cohorts (cohort study)	Not assessed	Micro- and nanoplastics polymers (placenta)	Inflammation-related proteomics (cord blood) & metabolomics (placenta, cord blood)
IMP TOX	School children (N=1156), age 6-18; 44.6% of them showed a positive allergenic reaction (15 inhalation	Air sampling International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood Questionnaire	Micro- and nanoplastics (EBC, stool)	Inflammation (blood, stool)

	allergens and 16 food allergens tested by Skin prick test)	Food Frequency Questionnaire Socioeconomic questionnaire		
plasticheal	Chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients in pre-dialysis stage (N = 27) Healthy controls (N = 12)	Life style habits (questionnaire)	Microplastics (>10 µm) (blood) Nanoplastics (< 10 µm) (blood)	Inflammation (blood)

In the **AURORA** Household Plastics Study, pregnant or breastfeeding participants or those with insufficient literacy to complete questionnaires were excluded. Subject to the recruitment/follow-up methods, participants without internet connections were also excluded, although uncommon nowadays.

In the **POLYRISK** project, inclusion and exclusion criteria were mostly harmonized across studies. Key exclusion criteria included recent use of immunosuppressive or anti-allergic medications, known asthma, COPD, a history of cardiovascular disease, active smoking, and pregnancy. Since the football field and traffic studies were designed as interventional repeated-measures studies, they also aligned on participant age, focusing on young adults. Participants in all studies completed extensive questionnaires, which were later used for post-hoc statistical adjustments to account for unforeseen confounders.

In **PlasticHeal**, all healthy workers whose activities could expose them to MNPs and unexposed volunteers were included. Healthy subjects are defined by absence of evidence of any active or chronic disease. Pregnant women were excluded from the study. In addition, as several of the assessed effect biomarkers were related to the induction of genotoxicity, volunteers with a recent X-ray examination were also excluded. As in other projects, an extensive questionnaire was completed by all participants. Similar criteria were adopted in **PlasticsFate**.

4.3 Recruitment strategies

To achieve the recruitment of a sufficient number of workers, various strategies could be implemented in the future:

- An announcement on the CUSP website (<https://cusp-research.eu/>) and in the social media channels of the CUSP project
- Already existing worker cohorts which correspond to eligibility criteria could be approached in order to establish a collaboration
- CUSP consortium members could make use of contacts established from *ad hoc* surveys implemented within a specific project
- CUSP consortium members can distribute the aforementioned survey in companies where they have already established a personal contact with directors, managers, or workers. Such personal contacts are known to help establishing a trustful climate and increase the likelihood of companies' participation in the research project. Both top-down (direct contact through managers or health & safety specialists) and bottom-up (indirect contact establishment with company manager through workers) recruitment approaches can be used.

Possible constraints due to organizational and logistical reasons, could limit the number of companies involved and thus should be carefully considered.

In occupational studies, a recruitment database should be created and progressively filled in upstream from and during the whole recruitment campaign. This file will gather relevant information on company workforce and contact details from managers and/or health and safety specialists. Emphasis will be made on the recruitment of workers from companies with known exposure to MNPs, while ensuring sample representativeness and between-company comparability of working conditions. This implies a priority focus on the recruitment of companies with the biggest workforce size, i.e., ensuring homogeneity in terms of external exposure nature and extent. Moreover, since human biomonitoring should focus on particle released during working activities instead of plastic manufacturing from chemicals, priority will be given to the recruitment of companies characterized by well identified release scenarios and concerned with handling plastics goods.

The CUSP Partners have followed different strategies to date. For instance, in **ImpTox** the recruitment procedure was conducted in Croatian schools (primary and secondary), after obtaining permission from the national authorities (Croatian Ministry of Science, Education and Young) and the school authorities. The schools helped organize parent/caregiver and school staff meetings with health care professionals from the Srebrnjak Children's Hospital where the study was presented and the parents/caregivers were able to get information on their and their child's participation in the study to their satisfaction. Schools in distinct regions of Croatia were offered to join **ImpTox** project in unbiased manner, assuming the location of the school meets projects requirement. Participant's parents have signed informed consent and filled out required questionnaires. Prior to any procedures, participants (and their parents/caregivers) needed to sign an informed consent for participation in the study. All children underwent a skin prick test (SPT) to a standard palette of inhaled allergens and common food allergens and they (their parents/caregivers) have been asked to fill out questionnaires on their personal and family history of allergy, dietary and lifestyle habits as well as consumer awareness and perception of MNPs. Blood (serum) samples have been taken, as well as stool samples at the time of recruitment and approximately 6 months after.

Being concerned with a working population, **PlasticsFate** pilot studies relied on the collaboration with the company's occupational physician. The company was informed in advance and in detail about the role of this research and the significance of the results of the analyses, both environmental and biological. Employees were enrolled as part of periodic or preventive health surveillance to ensure the least invasiveness possible. In addition, the protocol decided by the doctor in charge, in agreement with the employer, was evaluated in order to minimise the impact of the research activities on the working routine of the personnel. An informed consent form was carefully prepared for workers who wished to participate in the study to sign, and at the same time the worker was given an information sheet on the purpose of the study and the methods of analysis used. Urine and blood were collected at the beginning of the work shift. A questionnaire was administered to the participants, which included personal data, work history (job title, job description, years of exposure, previous work experience), personal history (lifestyle habits such as smoking, alcohol, most frequently used water), pathological history (near and distant), family history and pharmacological history. The presence of medical staff during the collection of the questionnaires ensured that the information was collected correctly and that the meaning of the questionnaires was clearer to the worker. A similar recruitment approach was implemented by **PlasticHeal**, which interviewed multiple companies of

the textile and recycling sectors. Invitations to participate in the studies were also sent through the involvement of plastic industry associations.

The **AURORA** Household Plastics Study followed up women of reproductive age for three months. After participants have expressed interest in participating, the researchers emailed the participants to answer any questions about the study and gave the participants the opportunity to schedule a phone call to discuss any questions. When there are no questions remaining, the first home visit is scheduled. At the first visit the participants were given another opportunity to ask questions before informed consent is collected by the researcher, and the participant is given a glass petri dish to collect a household dust sample following instructions. After the sample collection period (four weeks), the researchers visited the house for the second time to collect blood and urine samples. At this point, the participants also filled in an online questionnaire which collects information about their baseline characteristics, plastic-related behaviors, and household determinants of body plastic burden. Two months after the first biological samples were collected, participants were instructed to collect a second household dust sample. After the second dust sample collection period (four weeks), the researchers revisited the participants for the third home visit to collect blood and urine samples again. At this point, the participants filled in a follow-up plastic determinants and covariates questionnaire about their plastic-related behaviors. After completion of the third home visit and questionnaire, the participants completed their participation in the study.

In the **POLYRISK** project the volunteers for the general population were recruited by announcing the study on institutional websites and by direct contacting of football clubs and schools with a sport specialisation in the case of the football study. The textile companies were contacted using established contacts.

4.4 Control participants

In occupational studies, workers exposed to MNPs (exposed group) are compared with control participants. To this purpose, the control group, should consist of people with confirmed absence of occupational exposure to in their occupational settings.

Once enrolled, workers' names and contact details are entered in a specific numeric database, enabling the set-up of the workers registry to be followed up as a prospective cohort. Participating companies and workers are characterized using questionnaires. The epidemiological questionnaire is administered either as paper copies or using other methods (i.e., the REDCap software (<https://projectredcap.org/>) installed on tablets). Evaluation of potential confounding variables (i.e., workers' smoking status) will ensure representativeness of our convenience sample to be taken into account for analyses and result generalizability.

Ideally, 80 and 40 workers should be recruited for the exposed and control groups, respectively. However, these numbers were not achieved by any of the CUSP projects dealing with occupational studies due to the low involvement of companies and workers in this type of studies.

The rationale for calculating sample sizes in other type of studies is explained in **Annex 1**.

Procedures relative to informed consent acquisition, confidentiality and data safety are detailed in the next Section.

The **ImpTox** clinical study included both allergic and non-allergic (control) participants, preferably in a 1:2 ratio, and at least 210 (70 allergic and 140 non-allergic children) participants per region.

The **AURORA** Household Plastics Study has no control group due to the proof-of-concept nature and study design.

In the **POLYRISK** textile study, the control group consisted of office workers from the same factories who were not involved in the production process. The traffic and football field studies did not include a separate control group, as measurements were taken from the same individuals under different exposure scenarios. To minimize the influence of everyday exposure, participants in the traffic study were selected from a specific area of Utrecht, while in the football field study participants were drawn from the same school class. To ensure robustness and generalizability, sample size calculations were conducted for each study during the planning phase. These calculations were performed using specialized software, such as G*Power, or by simulating expected outcomes for key endpoints using the R programming language.

Workers of other companies not expected to be exposed to MNPs during their occupational activities were used on control groups in **PlasticHeal** and **PlasticsFate** studies.

5. HUMAN SUBJECTS AND DATA PROTECTION

5.1 Informed consent

Written informed consent should be acquired from volunteers and workers prior to enrolment in the studies. During the information visit in the field site, all volunteers are informed on the study scope, objectives and procedures, especially regarding exposure monitoring and biological matrices sampling. The consent should be written in the participant's native language. To the greatest extent possible, the patient information sheet and consent form should be written in non-technical, non-scientific, simple language. The information includes information on aim and scope of the study as well as the number and type of biological samples. Risks of the study are also explained in detail.

A detailed explanation on the risks and benefits participants can expect from the study is made orally by a local expert from the Project's institutions. Participants should be informed that their data, as well as their samples will be investigated in a coded form only for research purposes.

A consent form containing written information on all the above-mentioned study-related topics is distributed. Participants should be given time for consideration and an opportunity to ask questions. We explicitly state that participation is voluntary and that anyone has the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw their participation, samples or data at any time, without any consequences. We also explain how biological samples and data are collected, protected during the project and either destroyed or reused subsequently. Furthermore, we state what procedures are implemented in the event of unexpected or incidental findings (in particular, whether the participants have the right to know, or not to know, about any such findings).

In research Projects like **ImpTox**, children represent a vulnerable population in research and clinical studies. However, a body of evidence shows that exposure and events in early life and childhood significantly impacts our health status and disease later in life (adulthood and elderly age), the findings of this study may give better insight into the effect of harmful environmental exposure (to

MNPs) to the onset and pathophysiology of chronic diseases, including allergy. These findings cannot be reproduced in other (non-vulnerable) subjects, since we presume MNPs act in a cumulative manner and their effect may only be visible later in life.

Parents/legal guardians, receive a full verbal and written explanation about the intent, significance, implications and risks of the **ImpTox** scientific research study from the specified study physician. The parents/legal guardians have to agree that the child may participate in the above-named scientific research study and that the anonymized data collected may be used in any follow-up research. Their participation in the study is entirely voluntary and they are free to withdraw their consent for participation from the study at any time, without giving any reason, and without any of their child's medical care or legal rights being affected. Parents/legal guardian for the children cohort receive written information about the handling of any data obtained in the study. They are informed that their data is anonymized with a number code, but that auditing persons, who are bound by professional confidentiality, i.e., from regulatory bodies as the ethical committee may gain insight in the original data for inspection purposes.

Additionally, a study physician is present and answer any questions that may arise. The parents/legal guardians should confirm that participation in this study is voluntary, and that they understand that non-participation or revoking consent bear no negative consequences for them or their child. They should also confirm that they have received, read and understood the written explanation of the study and had the opportunity to ask any questions. The parents/legal guardians consent only after they have received answers to their satisfaction and have had sufficient time to understand the material and have formed a decision.

5.2 Confidentiality and coding process

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) applies to all information collected during the research with humans. The processing of information is based on the principles of correctness, lawfulness and transparency and the protection of confidentiality and rights pursuant to Legislative Decree No. 196/2003 and pursuant to EU Regulation 2016/679. Access to the data by study personnel should be restricted and data should be stored on a dedicated and secure server.

Upon enrolment in the study (i.e., signed informed consent form), workers and volunteers are assigned a code number in a way that does not disclose his/her identity, while still permitting the ability to identify the person for notification purposes. The key assigning persons' identity and contact details to personal code are recorded in an Excel type document, stored on the secured server from the principal investigator's institution, separately from all other study documents. Only people with a justified need to know will have access to this key document. Persons' names are entered in a second numeric file (worker/volunteer registry) stored on the secured server, separately from the key document assigning code labels and from all other study documents. This registry will enable cohort set-up and follow-up. Only people with a justified need to know will have access to these key documents. All other participant mentions, whether on a paper document, in a numeric file, in the electronic Case Report Form (eCRF) or on a biological sample pertaining to any phase of the study, are code-labelled.

All data, in accordance with current legislation, will be processed in an aggregate and anonymous way, by electronic means, for the preparation of scientific reports in which the individual subjects

will not be identifiable in any way. For paper questionnaires, the data are uploaded manually by the researchers to an excel file and the identification code is assigned when the data is entered on the file.

For the processing of the results of the questionnaire, the identification codes will be omitted, the only information that would allow associating a specific code with certain answers. Only part of the code used for the questionnaires will be used to identify biological samples. The decoding of biological samples will be made known only to the researchers involved in the project.

Data and samples collected on volunteers and workers, and companies are strictly confidential and cannot be communicated to third parties. All collaborators working on the study are assigned to the respect of participants' privacy. Volunteer and company confidentiality is also strictly guaranteed in the frame of any result publication in reports, scientific journals and congresses.

Data relating to questionnaires and biological analyzes will be shared between the researchers participating in the project. The data relating to biological determinations will be shared only with the competent doctors/health care personnel of the companies and entities that have made themselves available. As these are not diagnostic tests, but biological indicators of early and reversible effect, sensitive but not very specific, the results should always be communicated at the group level. For complying with the GDPR, all projects have involved the corresponding data protection officer (DPO) and disclosure his/her contact details to the research participants.

5.3 Withdrawal from the study

Participants and, in the case of patients or children, their parents/caregivers may revoke consent for participation in the study, as well as the use of the child's data, at any time, without reason and without any negative consequences for themselves or the child. Informed consent has to be signed by adult participants and parents/legal guardian and by the study physician. The study protocol and all relevant information regarding the project research will be presented to the children themselves in an adequate manner and these children will have the right to ask any questions. If they wish, they may ask to obtain study related information without the presence of their parents/legal guardians and they will have the right not to consent to participating in this study even if their parents/legal guardians already have consented. However, they cannot be recruited in the study if they themselves wish to participate, but their parents/legal guardians do not agree.

5.4 Data centralization, management and storage

The participating centers will keep a screening log and a patient recruitment list. The patient recruitment list also contains the contact information. All personal data (name, date of birth, address and telephone number) is thus be stored separately from any clinical data. Each participant receives a number code, which is taken from a continuous list of numbers on the recruitment list, for pseudonymisation of all data. Personal data including participant name, date of birth, address, gender and the date on which they were recruited in the study are collected, as well as participants' clinical and all other data, including height, weight, full medical history, family medical history, diagnosis, infection history, medication usage and all clinical data obtained in the course of the study are handled in complete confidence, following good ethical and legal practice.

Collected blood, stool and other biological samples and data about the participant are given a unique study number (participant`s code) to protect their identity and ensure complete confidentiality. This number only, and not the participant`s name or any other identification data, are marked on the stored blood samples and other data. Staff performing the tests on samples do not know the participants` identity. Any information or sample that leaves the hospital/laboratory have participant`s name and all other identification data removed so that the participant cannot be identified, and the samples will be tracked and kept secure, in order not to be lost at any point. Data collected during the study may be sent to associate researchers, but we are taking all reasonable steps to protect participants` privacy (the data released will be fully anonymized). Also, the data from the studies are stored both electronically and in paper copies, in accordance with current regulations (i.e., GCP).

To ensure data security and confidentiality, all necessary electronic transfers are done using secure platforms (i.e., FileCare). Once files are available, the recipient receives an e-mail inviting him/her to retrieve the documents. In this purpose, a unique personal password is required. This password is generated for each document batch at the moment of data transfer, and communicated to the recipient via his/her professional mobile phone. The principal investigator is responsible for ensuring proper receipt and storage of all data and documents in the Organization server. All numeric data files are stored on the secured server, separately from the worker registry and key document assigning specific codes to participants` identity. Code-labelled paper documents are stored in a locked file cabinet and environmental samples in laboratory freezers, for the duration of the study and any required records retention period. Only study team members with a justified need to know have access to the cabinet key and freezers.

5.5 Health and safety plan for collaborators

In occupational studies, field campaigns are conducted directly within participating company facilities. Chemical and physical hazards encountered at company sites may include MNPs and their additives. During the information visit conducted by a representative of the operational team (preferably an occupational hygienist) the site safety and health plan are discussed. This includes asking the company representative what types of recognized hazards the facility may contain, which includes physical, chemical, and biological hazards, as well as the types of personal protective equipment required by the facility. The collaborator in charge of the information visit is responsible for informing the rest of the operational team on site-specific safety and health plan. Based on the team professional judgement, at least the minimum required personal protective equipment by the company (if not higher levels of protection) are worn by all operational team members, at all times. Upon arriving to the facility, any prescribed training to enter the facility is completed. Once the operational team has entered the site, all site-specific health and safety plans are to be followed. All collaborators are obliged to comply with relevant ethical and professional standards (GCP, GLP, GMP etc.) and have to sign a Material transfer agreement prior to sharing biological samples.

6. STUDY VARIABLES AND OUTCOMES

6.1 Exposure assessment

Considering human external exposure, the inhalation exposure route could be more common in occupational environments, where various sources for both primary and secondary airborne MNPs can exist in different processes and working environments. Even though accurate estimates are

lacking due to the huge variability, we should take into account that MNPs are frequently present in air, especially indoors (i.e., carpets, clothing etc releasing fibres). Hence, inhalation is also the most relevant exposure route in the studies performed by **AURORA** and **ImpTox**.

Most CUSP Partners have implemented procedures aimed at the definition of an adequate sampling protocol for determining the concentration of MNPs in complex occupational settings as well as indoor and outdoor environments, i.e., general population exposure settings (**Table 2**). The strategy for exposure assessment can vary depending on the environmental conditions of the exposure scenario. The measurement strategy is based on active sampling with both static and personal sampling, combined with particle monitoring in relevant locations or processes and tasks. The air sampling should utilize appropriate collection substrate to be able to perform chemical analyses from the sample. The real time monitoring should be covering different particle sizes from nanometer sizes to micrometer sizes.

The air sampling methods for different purposes are found in various types and qualities, but modern standards (i.e., EN689, EN481, EN482, EN16966, EN17058) for exposure monitoring and assessment give reliable basis for selection of appropriate methods and strategies. Generally, two types of sampling methods are used for air sampling: passive and active sampling. In the passive sampling, the air sample is collected based on natural diffusion and permeation when sample is adhered to absorbent/substrate. In the active sampling the sampled air is pumped onto substrate (filter) with controlled and suitable air flow. Passive sampling is ideal for long term average concentrations while active sampling is preferred for real-time monitoring or when high temporal resolution is needed. With active sampling there is more control and higher sensitivity than in the passive sampling, and for example for the occupational studies, i.e., occupational exposure limit (OEL) compliance, the active sampling is used. The active air sampling to determine the aerosol (air) concentrations in i.e., working environment can be basically performed in two ways, depending on the aim of the study. The personal sampling from the breathing zone of a person (i.e., worker) gives most accurate information of individual exposure, but sometimes a stationary air sampling from a certain area, workstation etc. can give valuable information of studied impurities (particles, MNPLs etc) in the surrounding air.

Typically, in occupational studies, both personal and stationary air samplings are performed simultaneously in order to have valuable information from different exposure situations, locations and sources of emissions. The sampling times can vary, with relation to the object of the study (i.e., OEL compliance studies have typically 8 h sampling representing a whole workday), but also to the actual concentrations in air when the analytical limitations must be considered. Both personal and static samplers are based on using air pump to suck air through sample collection substrate (typically thin filter material). For personal measurement, the system is light and small to be carried out by the person for a period of time (8 h in occupational studies), and in stationary sampling the pumps (and hence the pump's air flow) can be much larger to collect higher amounts of sample air to the filter, which can be in some cases beneficial.

For the MNPs studies, one essential requirement for the method should be that it would allow the analyses of the collected sample in terms of physical, chemical and/or biological characteristics, i.e., with MNPs the plastic types, sizes and shapes. Many traditional sampling methods are collecting sample for gravimetric analyses with i.e., elemental/chemical analyses possibilities included, but

these specific analyses are not often suitable for MNPs materials analyses. This requirement is targeted especially to the selection of appropriate sample collection substrate, the sampling filter material, which shall not disturb the chemical analyses.

When air sampling campaign is carried out, a lot of necessary information, i.e., contextual information, shall be collected concerning the studied and sampled situation. The purpose of the measurement, product/substance information, determinants of exposure, sampling procedure, sampling method and also other relevant observations are important and necessary information for exposure and risk assessment.

In addition to collecting air samples, the online (or real time) monitoring of particle levels in the air can be useful method to exposure assessment. However, there are limitations and features regarding the applicability of these methods that need to be considered. While these methods can give information of i.e., time resolved concentrations with high time resolution, particle sizes, concentration changes during measurement etc. they cannot identify the measured particles or characterize their morphology (i.e., fibres vs. spherical particles vs. other types). Therefore, in any measurement, an additional method is needed to verify and characterize the measured particles if the identification is essential (as it is when studying MNPs exposure, which can consist of several different types of plastics with different morphologies). Especially in occupational studies, the real time monitoring can be useful in i.e., detecting process stages with higher emissions, locating sources of emission, detecting emission air flows in the working area etc. Usually, these measurements require the use of several monitoring devices simultaneously to be able to distinguish between processes related particles from the background particles, which are common in all areas and environment (with exception of clean rooms).

Many occupational environments contain aerosols from wide range of sizes. Regarding the inhalation exposure, the nature and size of the particles have an effect on the deposition and behaviour in the human respiratory system. Traditionally, in occupational hygiene, the different size fractions of particulate matter of aerosols have been inhalable, thoracic and respirable fractions (EN 481). Additionally, usually in aerosol science and environmental and general population studies, the size fractions of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and PM₁ have been considered. With some differences in the definitions among size fractions, the smaller sizes, i.e., respirable fraction (or PM_{2.5}/PM₁) are considered having increased risk for health effects due to small size and ability to penetrate to the gas exchange region of the lung. This applies also to studies with MNPLs as there is evidence of very small MNPLs particles found in occupational as well as in indoor and outdoor environments.

Outdoors and indoors scenarios (including occupational settings) can rely on similar strategy. Basic exposure assessment measurement strategy should include active sampling, either static or personal, with appropriate sampling collection substrate to be able to perform chemical analyses from the sample. The real time monitoring can be used if there is interest to follow changes in the particle concentrations during the measurement time.

All the CUSP projects except **AURORA** performed air measures and sampling. The **AURORA** Household Plastics Study collected household dust to evaluate if house dust levels of MNPs contribute to human MNP burden. The whole study comprised of three home visits. During the first home visit, the researchers assisted the participants with setting up the bottom half of two glass petri

dishes in the living room at a height of ± 1.2 meters from the ground, following the protocol of Soltani and co-workers (Soltani et al., 2021). The tops of the petri dishes were wrapped in tin foil and put in a non-plastic storage envelope until the end of the sampling period. The petri dishes were left in the living room for one month. The petri dishes were collected during the second home visit, when the researchers returned to collect the biological samples. When the researchers arrived, the petri dishes were rewrapped in tin foil and placed in the envelope and brought back to the research centre. During the second home visit, the researchers also left a new envelope with two more petri dishes and instructions for the participants to set them up themselves in the same location one month before the second round of biological samples were collected. The second set of petri dishes was collected when the researchers returned to collect the follow up biological samples during the third home visit. Field and lab blanks were collected for each phase of sample collection to quantify any potential contamination.

Collected household dust were measured using pyrolysis gas chromatography mass spectrometry (Pyr-GC/MS). MNP deposition rate ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$) was calculated by dividing the polymer mass by the number of collection days while adjusting for the petri dish area. In addition, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to analyse the microscopic features of the detected MNPs (i.e., size, shape, pigment) that cannot be captured by Pyr-GC/MS.

FTIR spectroscopy is, together with Raman spectroscopy, the most commonly used state of the art analytical methods in microplastic research. FTIR enables the identification of polymer types, their abundance, shape, and size. Focal plane array (FPA) based micro-FTIR spectroscopy allows the identification of particles in a size range from 10 to 500 μm , whereas particles exceeding 500 μm can be analysed by attenuated total reflectance (ATR)- FTIR spectroscopy (Möller et al., 2020).

Raman- and FTIR-based chemical imaging complement each other and should be chosen in accordance with the specific research questions: The Raman imaging run time is significantly higher than FTIR imaging (Käppler et al., 2016), but is independent of the shape, size, or thickness of the measured particles, which can influence the results in micro-FTIR imaging. Black particles often result in unidentifiable FTIR-spectra, due to the high absorption of infrared radiation. For both vibrational spectroscopy methods, a thorough sample purification is needed prior to the concentration on the filter surface on which the analysis takes place. Both FTIR and Raman analysis of air filters were performed within the **PlasticHeal** project

Like FTIR or Raman spectroscopy, hyperspectral imaging is a nonbiased, non-destructive identification method, giving information on the spatial position, size, and specific reflectance spectrum of objects.

Special care must be taken to minimize and monitor potential contamination of the samples during sample processing. Therefore, all media used during sample processing must be pre-filtered (mesh sizes should be smaller than the limit of detection of NMP particle sizes). A cotton lab coat should be worn, and filtering devices and all used tools should be made of glass or stainless steel and cleaned before being used with pre-filtered ethanol and pre-filtered water (mesh sizes should be smaller than the limit of detection of NMP particle sizes). If possible, all sample handling steps should be performed under laminar air flow boxes to minimize airborne contamination. In any case, procedural blanks must be performed during the complete sample processing steps.

Although CUSP Partners have become more familiar with exposure by considering mainly inhalation pathway, we could recognize that an estimation of oral exposure done based on the questionnaire, where diet and other life-style habits are recorded, may also be of primary importance for subgroups of people belonging to the general population. However, whereas the measurement and quantification of airborne particles at the breathing zone of workers can give quantitative estimates, dietary intakes are rather explorative and can give qualitative or semi-quantitative estimates.

6.2 Biomarkers

Biomonitoring studies aim to investigate whether measurable and quantifiable MNPs emission may impact on human health by measuring biomarkers of exposure and of early effects in workers occupationally exposed in selected exposure scenarios, or in the general population. In a recent review, Panizzolo and co-workers (Panizzolo et al., 2023) highlight the lack of human studies regarding the exposure to MNPs in occupational settings. Moreover, this review suggests common pathways across the species, as well as similarities in mechanisms of action of MNPs with other foreign particulates in determining biochemical changes or overt health effects.

Lesson learned in EU-funded Projects on nano-objects and ultrafine particles suggests that biomarkers should ideally be measured in biological matrices collected non-invasively (or by minimally-invasive procedures) to enable a routine screening and monitoring of workers and volunteers. Although some recent investigations have found MNPs in stool and in induced sputum samples (Ramsperger et al., 2023), the protocols adopted by CUSP Partners were focusing mainly on three biological matrices, namely exhaled breath condensate (EBC), urine and blood. By cooling a subject's exhaled breath in a non-invasive way, it is possible to collect a liquid composed mainly of water and a very small amount of airway lining fluids. Exhaled breath condensate (EBC), a non-invasive matrix predominantly composed of water vapour and small droplets from various regions of the respiratory tract, is considered a valuable biological sample to monitoring exposure when biological monitoring using traditional biological matrices such as urine or blood become more challenging (i.e., for dusts or respirable crystalline silica) (Forest & Pourchez, 2023). However, for specific investigations, i.e., to assess the gut dysbiosis or characterize the microbiome, stool sampling should be also considered because it can provide relevant information.

The presence of foreign particles is a common finding and its relationship with health outcomes has never been clarified. These findings lead us to propose a minimum set of biomarkers, to be assessed in biological matrices of volunteers and workers with potential exposure to MNPs. This can be further complemented with recently validated biomarkers (Ghelli et al., 2022; Hemmendinger et al., 2023) reflecting long-term endpoints, such as chronic inflammation and fibrosis, as well as cardiovascular endpoints, considering possible interference in lipid metabolism.

6.2.1 Biomarkers of exposure

Providing objective demonstration of the absorption of chemicals and/or particles in the body, exposure biomarkers can be useful in toxicology for a more accurate risk assessment, reducing misclassification in health studies.

6.2.1.1 Characterization of micro- and nano-sized plastics in biological fluids

Measuring particles in EBC could help giving an estimate of particle retention in the lungs. Its rationale is based on the assumption that insoluble particles may behave differently according to their physico-chemical parameters, mainly size which, in turn, can affect their aerodynamic behavior. Whereas particles $< 0.26 \mu\text{m}$ evade macrophages, particle $< 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ diffuse and thus can have a high penetration; particles from 0.1 to $< 1 \mu\text{m}$ are subjected to diffusion/sedimentation; particles from 1 to $< 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ can impact lower airways, whereas particles $> 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ deposit in the upper airways. Nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) have been used for the quantification of particles in biological matrices, such as EBC, and can thus support the assessment of internal dose of particles as an exposure biomarker (Guseva Canu et al., 2023). NTA is a method for visualizing and analyzing particles in liquids that relates the rate of Brownian motion to particle size. The rate of movement is related only to the viscosity and temperature of the liquid; it is not influenced by particle density or refractive index. NTA allows the determination of a size distribution profile of small particles with a diameter of approximately 10 - 1000 nanometers (nm) in liquid suspension. NTA captures the Brownian motion of each particle in a video. The hydrodynamic diameter of the particles is determined based on the Stokes-Einstein relation starting from the obtained diffusion coefficient (size range 30 - 2000 nm). The particles concentration can be determined by counting all objects in the field of view and knowing the measured volume. A limit of detection (LOD) of 5×10^5 NPs/mL was calculated (Panizzolo et al., 2024). To date, the main limitation of such an approach is the lack of characterization of polymers and of chemical composition of particles.

6.2.1.2 Molecular Imaging techniques

The detection of MNPs in complex human matrices, such as EBC, urine, saliva and blood has shown to be a challenging task, mostly because of the strong organic background from human samples that overlaps with the signals of the particle and aggravates reliable detection of MNPs. There are two main approaches for the MNPs detection: thermo-analytical and spectroscopic ones (Braun et al., 2018). Thermo-analytical methods, such as Py-GC-MS or TED-GC-MS (Garcia et al., 2024; Leslie et al., 2022; Marfella et al., 2024) are suitable for the determination of the type of polymer and their mass concentration. However, they cannot distinguish between polymers and polymer based particulate matter. Additionally, TED-GC-MS has only been established for detection of micro plastics in environmental samples (Goedecke et al., 2022). These tools are also not able to provide information regarding particle number, size, shape and morphology. Spectroscopic tools include mostly confocal Raman microscopy (CRM), Fourier transform infrared microscopy (μFTIR) and attenuated total reflection FTIR microscopy ($\mu\text{ATR-FTIR}$). These molecular imaging techniques are the only methods that allow the simultaneous chemical identification, visualization and characterization of MNPs. That includes the determination of the concentration of the particles as well as size, shape distribution and surface properties of singular particles ranging from nano to micro size.

There are still only a limited number of publications for characterization of MNPs in biological fluids and matrices by means of spectroscopic tools. μFTIR was used to detect various MNPs (PS, PE, PP and PTFE) in the urine in healthy donors and donors that suffer from endometriosis (Rotchell et al., 2024). The results showed that samples from donors with endometriosis contain almost twice the number of MPs that was found in samples from healthy donors. The size of detected particles ranged

from 19 μm to 400 μm . Number concentration of micro-particles was found to be ca. 500 particles/L. μFTIR was also applied for the detection of MNPs in the blood samples of healthy donors, where numerous polymers were identified in 90 % of the donors (Leonard et al., 2024). Micro-particles from 7 μm to 3000 μm with the concentration 2500 particles/L were identified in the blood samples. Analysis of human feces (Hartmann et al., 2024), vein tissues (Rotchell et al., 2023) and human lungs (Jenner et al., 2022) by means of μFTIR reveals a very low amount of microplastics larger than 5 μm with a concentration of ca. 3.5, 15 and 1.4 particles/g, respectively. To improve diffraction limited spatial resolution Raman based spectroscopic methods were applied to reach a resolution of about 300 nm. Raman spectroscopy and Raman microspectroscopy were used for the detection of microplastics in thrombocytes of human blood, urine as well as in exhaled breath condensate (EBC). Plastic particles ranging from 2.1 to 26 μm in thrombocytes, from 3 to 13 μm in urine as well as from 1.6 to 126 μm in EBC were detected (Geng et al., 2023; Massardo et al., 2024; D. Wu et al., 2023). None of the studies mentioned above were able to detect nano-sized particles ($< 1\mu\text{m}$). These methods and approaches are still under development to identify, characterize and quantify plastic particles having toxicological relevant sizes, smaller than 5 μm in diameter for the inhalation route.

Due to the lack of data on nano-sized plastics and toxicologically relevant micro-particles in human fluids, CRM was developed and validated in the framework of **PlasticHeal** project in terms of visualization, chemical identification and quantification of MNPLs smaller than 5 μm in human blood, EBC and urine. Analysis by means of CRM consists of two levels: i) coupling of CRM with particle searching algorithm that allows analysis of large sample areas; this can be used for fast screening of a sample ii) chemical imaging of a smaller area for more detailed analysis; this can be used for analyzing nano-sized particles. For both approaches a detailed Raman databased (ST Japan) was used for the correct chemical identification of the detected particles. For method validation water, blood, urine and EBC samples were spiked with known concentrations of PS and PET nano-sized particles (200 nm, 500 nm and 1 μm). The samples were digested using an adapted protocol by Löder and co-workers (Löder et al., 2017) and subsequently filtrated on Anodisc filters (pore size 20 nm) to enrich and evenly distribute the sample in a defined area. Achieved recovery of mass and number concentrations ranged from 75 to 100 % depending on certain biological fluids. Limit of detection and quantification was measured to be 15 ppb at the filtrated volume of 10 mL.

The adapted and validated CRM towards identification of nano-sized particles in bio-fluids was successfully applied for analysis of EBC and blood samples of various workers at different occupational settings. Most prominent MNPs detected in these samples from workers were PP, PS, PET, PE as well as metal oxide nanoparticles, such as TiO_2 and CeO_2 . Size of detected plastic particles ranged from 300 nm to 6 μm . Up to 5×10^6 particles/L and 1.5×10^6 particles/L have been detected in blood and EBC samples, respectively. About 40% of detected particles revealed the size under 1 μm . The huge number of nano-sized particles in human fluids may have strong effects on human health and have not been revealed by other studies yet.

6.2.2 Biomarkers of early effect

A biomarker of effect is defined as “*any measurable biochemical, physiological, or other alteration within an organism that, depending on magnitude, can be recognized as an established or potential health impairment or disease*” (Henderson et al., 1989). Biomarkers should not be considered as diagnostic tests, but rather as indicators reflecting early modifications preceding progressive

structural or functional damage at the molecular, cellular, and tissue level, i.e., changes possibly leading to adverse effects but completely reversible (except in the case of mutations) upon the removal from the exposure of concern. Biomarkers of effect can be used to evaluate whether a well-characterized exposure is associated with a shift in the distribution of relevant biochemical or functional endpoints, indicative of early changes in the target or critical organs/tissue. To assess such early events associated with exposure to MNPs, at present, we can rely on a panel of biomarkers with well-known pathophysiological meaning reflecting local and systemic oxidative stress, systemic inflammation, and genotoxicity changes.

To date, no published human biomonitoring studies exist that evaluate the potential effects of MNP exposure. This is probably due to the lack of reliable techniques that allow detecting MNPs in human samples. In fact, most of the recent publications using human samples focus on the development of such techniques, which has resulted on the detection of MNP in a broad variety of human tissues and organs, such as blood, liver, lung, colon, placenta, etc. (i.e., as reviewed by Thompson et al., 2024).

6.2.2.1 Biomarkers of local and systemic inflammation

Inflammation is a physiological condition implemented by living organisms to counteract foreign stimuli including pathogens, such as viruses, bacteria and fungi, inorganic and organic particles, such as plastics. Since local or systemic inflammation is the main outcome investigated following MNPs exposure, inflammatory biomarkers deserve greater importance for biomonitoring purposes.

A key role is played by cytokines, protein-based chemical mediators produced by a broad range of cells, including the immune cells recruited in the inflammation site. Various cytokines such as Interleukins 1-beta (IL-1 β), IL-6, IL-8 and IL-10 were used as biomarkers of inflammation in cell lines and animal studies. Some of them (IL-1 β , IL-6, Tumor Necrosis Factor alpha - TNF- α - and Interferon-gamma - INF- γ) are pro-inflammatory cytokines (Ghelli et al., 2022). For instance, in the review paper of Panizzolo and co-workers (Panizzolo et al., 2023), 5 out of 10 studies showed significant increases in IL-1 β levels in *in vitro* models after exposure to PE and PS. IL-6 levels also increased following exposure to MNPs (PS nanosphere) or PMMA (polymethyl methacrylate) and PVC of 50-310 nm in size; 11 studies showed an increase, 5 of them significant compared to controls. An increase in levels was also seen for TNF- α and INF- γ in 9 and 3 studies, respectively. On the other hand, IL-8 and IL-10 have a dual function, as they not only stimulate the production of other cytokines but are also involved in limiting their production. Indeed, after exposure to MNP, all articles reviewed have shown an increase in their levels, which are crucial for the regulation by negative feedback of pro-inflammatory cytokine production. The *in vitro* studies showed the inflammatory biomarkers as the main indicators of the perturbation occurring in biological systems and cell cultures challenged with different types of MNPs. *In vivo* animal models showed increasing levels for IL-1 β , IL-8, IL-10 in different tissues, such as gut, skin mucus, blood, and kidney after exposure to PS-NP (polystyrene beads) compared to control animal tissues, with some studies showing increasing trend levels of IL-1 β , IL-8, IL-10, TNF- α and INF- γ after exposure to PE, and PS 5-1 mm, 1-05 mm and 0.5- 0.1 mm.

TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-17, IL-4 and IL-10 can serve as biomarkers of inflammation and immune-suppression. TNF- α and IL-1 β cytokines are indicative of the recruitment and activation of pro-inflammatory Th1-lymphocytes, while IL-17 and IL-4 are produced upon pro-inflammatory stimuli to indicate macrophage recruitment and by Th2-lymphocytes to favor the maturation of B-

lymphocytes into plasma cells producing E-type antibodies (IgE), respectively. IL-4 is therefore indicative of allergic diseases. IL-10, on the other hand, is an immuno-suppressive cytokine, which reduces the recruitment of effector T-lymphocytes and counteracts the effects of TNF- α and IL-1 β . Furthermore, leukotriene B4 (LTB4), i.e., a neutrophil chemoattractant strongly increased in asthmatic reactions, and Clara Cell 16kD protein (CC16 pneumoprotein), and anti-inflammatory protein and biomarker of the airway barrier integrity, could serve as biomarkers of bronchial tract activation, permeability and local inflammation.

Finally, C Reactive Protein – CRP - can be analyzed by a highly sensitive assay (hs-CRP) as an explorative biomarker of vascular inflammation, as its level in EBC has been shown to correlate with that of serum, and can be used to monitor the presence of a local inflammation. Furthermore, hs-CRP is also considered a risk factor for coronary heart disease (Hadrup et al., 2020).

6.2.2.2 Biomarkers of oxidative stress

Oxidative stress (OS) is a central mechanism of action for both pulmonary and extra-pulmonary health effects of particulate matter (Mills et al., 2009) and several studies of exposure to particles in humans have applied biomarkers of oxidative damage in the blood compartment or in terms of products excreted in urine or EBC. Biomarkers include 8-hydroxy-guanosine (8OHG), i.e., a marker of oxidative DNA damages, 8-isoprostane and Malondialdehyde (MDA), whereas nitro-tyrosine is produced upon nitrosative stress. Both biomarkers increase in acute or chronic inflammation and indicate the recruitment and activation of neutrophils and macrophages.

Analysis of 8-isoprostane (15-F2t-Isoprostane) and malondialdehyde (MDA) indicate systemic OS, i.e., oxidative burden supported by the organism (Graille et al., 2020). 8-Isoprostanes are prostaglandin-like molecules independently generated by cyclooxygenase enzymes and radical-induced peroxidation of arachidonic acids. They are reliable biomarkers of lipid peroxidation because they are ubiquitous in the body, stable in biological fluids and not sensitive to dietary lipids intake. MDA is a biomarker of lipid hydroperoxides. This molecule can interact with nucleic acids leading to DNA adducts that, in turn, may generate mutations that can evolve into cancer. Many pathological conditions and certain airway exposures are associated with MDA increase in all biological matrices including EBC. To use MDA as a biomarker of OS in EBC, a reference interval has been tentatively defined (Turcu et al., 2022). It can be quantified colorimetrically following its controlled reaction with thiobarbituric acid reactive substance (TBARS). Modifications of TBARS concentrations are used to evaluate a wide range of human diseases, and MDA remains, to date, the most widely employed assay used to determine lipid peroxidation (Toto et al., 2022).

Biomarkers of OS that have been investigated both using *in vitro* and *in vivo* models are the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and MDA. ROS are formed as a normal attribute of aerobic life as a by-product of metabolic reactions. Of the 65 studies included in the review of Panizzolo and co-workers (Panizzolo et al., 2023), 12 out of 20 showed a statistically significant increase in ROS following exposure to different MNPs as compared to the control group.

In whole organisms, like those of every other living being, there are effective defense systems to balance an excess in ROS production, such as enzymes (i.e., SOD and CAT, which are present in

aerobic organisms. During the enzymatic SOD reactions, they make the superoxide radical less reactive, transforming it into molecular oxygen and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). H₂O₂ together with GPx (glutathione peroxidase) are used as biomarkers of oxidative stress. Several *in vitro* studies where human cell lines were exposed to varying concentrations of PS (from 25 to 1200 µg/ml) for a minimum of 4 h to a maximum of 48 h, have shown an initial downward trend in SOD enzyme activity in the first few hours, with small increases after 48 h (Cheng et al., 2022; Vecchiotti et al., 2021). Increased levels of MDA were found in 10 out of 14 studies dealing with MNPs (Panizzolo et al., 2023).

Like MDA, TAC or TAP (total antioxidant capacity or total antioxidant power) can be used to assess the cumulative effects of the antioxidants present in the matrices analysed, since TAC is a biomarker able to quantify the capacity of the human body to counteract oxidative stress. TAC is commonly investigated in relation to a variety of human diseases, including immune-mediated and inflammatory diseases. Studies in animal models showed a significant increase in TAC levels after 24 h following exposure to PET, and PE (Xiao et al., 2021).

6.2.2.3 Biomarkers of genotoxicity

Damage to the genetic material is of particular concern because it may result in heritable genetic disease or cancer (Albertini & Kaden, 2020). Among the biomarkers of effect, those used to detect DNA damage are of utmost importance (Annangi et al., 2016). They can detect either primary DNA damage, which could still be repaired, or damage that is already fixed at the gene or chromosome level. The latter, known as mutations, is more relevant as mutations are known initiators of the carcinogenic process (Albertini & Kaden, 2020). In fact, increased frequencies of micronuclei (MN) in human peripheral blood lymphocytes have been shown to be predictive for cancer risk (Bonassi et al., 2011).

Biomarkers of genotoxicity are classical effect biomarkers that have been extensively used in human biomonitoring studies as there is sufficient knowledge regarding their physiological roles (Rodríguez-Carrillo et al., 2023). Most widely used matrices for early genetic effects are blood, nasal and buccal cells. MN formation requires cell division. Hence, MN formed *in vivo* can directly be assessed in exfoliated epithelial cells from actively dividing tissues, such as buccal, nasal, and urothelial mucosa (Norppa & Falck, 2003). In the case of peripheral blood lymphocytes, most of which are in a resting G₀-stage, cells should be cultured *ex vivo* to allow MN expression. The inclusion of cytochalasin B, which arrests cytokinesis after cell division, allows restricting the analysis to cells that have divided only once as they are easily recognized by their binucleate appearance. The cytokinesis-block micronucleus (CBMN) is the most used method to assess MN in biomonitoring studies (Bolognesi & Fenech, 2019; Ladeira, 2024). The evaluation of MN in buccal cells provides a complementary method for assessing chromosome damage at the site of contact of many substances (i.e., ingested or inhaled MNPLs) instead of assessing systemic effects and serves as a robust biomarker for evaluating genotoxicity, reflecting cellular damage and chromosomal instability (Malacarne et al., 2022; Pinto et al., 2025). The rate of chromosomal damage can also be assessed in peripheral blood erythrocytes. Flow-cytometric analysis of MN in reticulocytes (MNRET) is a sensitive high-through-put method (Abramsson-Zetterberg, 2000) of high potential in biomonitoring studies (Costa et al., 2011; Montero-Montoya et al., 2020). The assay detects damage induced in bone marrow erythroblasts.

Among the CUSP projects, only **PlasticHeal** has assessed genotoxicity in human samples. Genotoxic effects have been assessed by the MN assay in peripheral blood lymphocytes and reticulocytes, and in buccal cells, as these assays have been considered the potential effect biomarkers covering carcinogenicity, including genotoxicity, in occupational exposure human biomonitoring studies by the European chapter of the International Society for Exposure Science (ISES Europe) and the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Occupational Biomonitoring activity of Working Parties of Hazard and Exposure Assessment group (Ladeira, 2024; Zare Jeddi et al., 2021). In addition, DNA damage has also been assessed by the comet assay in mononuclear blood cells, an approach broadly applied in human biomonitoring studies (Milić et al., 2021), and currently recognized as one of the most sensitive biomarkers for detecting initial DNA damage (Živković et al., 2024). The comet assay, also known as single-cell gel electrophoresis, is a highly versatile and sensitive technique for detecting different forms of DNA damage, particularly DNA strand breaks, as well as DNA repair processes at the level of individual cells (Azqueta et al., 2020). The assay has demonstrated utility in routine industrial testing and has been applied to assess the genotoxicity of airborne particulate matter, underscoring its sensitivity in detecting DNA damage in environmental samples (Buschini et al., 2001). Furthermore, it has been effectively used to detect DNA strand breaks induced by various nanomaterials, highlighting its critical role in assessing the potential health risks associated with these emerging contaminants (García-Rodríguez et al., 2019).

Although there is not available literature on genotoxic effects assessed in MNP exposed human populations, recent *in vivo* studies have reported significantly increased DNA damage (evaluated by the comet assay) in rat peripheral blood cells (Farag et al., 2023) and mouse spleen cells (Nikolic et al., 2022) orally administered with 3.75-60 mg/kg b.w. of PE (4-6 µm) for 35 d, and 0.01 or 0.1 mg/d of fluorescent PS (40 & 200 nm) for 5 w, respectively. DNA damage has also been reported in different cell lines after exposure to MNPs, mainly PS. The outcomes seem to be cell-line specific, depending on the differential uptake of particles and generation of ROS (Domenech et al., 2023). Similarly, increased MN levels were induced by PS (100 nm) in the fibroblastic Hs27 cell line (Poma et al., 2019) and by PE (10-45 µm) in human blood lymphocytes (Çobanoğlu et al., 2021), whereas no significant induction of MN could be observed in CHO-k1 cells treated with carboxylated PS (50 & 500 nm) (Hesler et al., 2019).

6.2.2.4 Biomarkers of gut dysbiosis

The gut microbiota refers to the complex and dynamic community of microorganisms—bacteria, viruses, fungi, and archaea—that inhabit the gastrointestinal tract. In humans, this microbial ecosystem is vast and influenced by numerous factors, including genetics, diet, age, and environmental exposures, resulting in a unique microbial signature for every individual (Hou et al., 2022). The gut microbiota performs critical functions essential for host health, facilitating the digestion and fermentation of complex carbohydrates, synthesizing essential vitamins like vitamin K and certain B vitamins, modulating immune system development, and acting as a protective barrier against pathogenic microorganisms. Additionally, the microbiota plays a role in maintaining intestinal integrity by supporting the gut lining and producing metabolites, such as short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), which contribute to anti-inflammatory and immune-regulatory processes (Den Besten et al., 2013; Jandhyala et al., 2015).

When this intricate microbial balance is disrupted, a state known as dysbiosis arises. Dysbiosis is characterized by alterations in microbial diversity and functionality, often favoring pathogenic or opportunistic species at the expense of beneficial ones. The implications of gut dysbiosis extend beyond gastrointestinal disorders. Altered gut microbiota composition has been linked to systemic inflammation, impaired metabolic processes, weakened immune responses, metabolic disorders such as obesity and diabetes, inflammatory conditions like inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), and even neuropsychiatric disorders via the gut-brain axis (Weiss & Hennet, 2017).

Emerging evidence suggests that the ingestion of MNPs can affect gut microbial composition by directly interacting with gut-resident microorganisms. On the other hand, indirect interactions and consequences might come through the production of inflammatory and OS responses in the gastrointestinal epithelium, facilitating the penetration of other pollutants and pathogens adhered in their surfaces, or through the leaching of plasticizers and the degradation into monomers (Fackelmann & Sommer, 2019). Exposure to MNPs of various types and sizes is known to induce gut microbiota dysbiosis (Jiménez-Arroyo et al., 2023), which can compromise the gut's epithelial barrier. This disruption may facilitate the distribution of MNPs throughout the body, with detrimental effects on health. Some biomarkers for detecting gut microbial dysbiosis in humans have been already described (Zwezerijnen-Jiwa et al., 2023). Thus, microbial biomarkers focus on the composition and diversity of the gut microbiota, identifying specific taxa or groups of microorganisms associated with health or disease states. Two main diversity metrics are widely used: (1) the alpha diversity, which measures within-sample diversity (i.e., Shannon index, Simpson index), reflecting the richness and evenness of microbial populations. Reduced alpha diversity is often indicative of dysbiosis, as observed in conditions like inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and obesity; and (2) the beta diversity, which assesses differences in microbial composition between samples, providing insights into shifts caused by dysbiosis (Rodriguez et al., 2025).

Moreover, the identification of specific taxa, genera or even species can be also associated to malfunction of the microbiome. For example, while the overgrowth of *Proteobacteria* or *Enterobacteriaceae* is often a marker of dysbiosis and inflammation the reduction in beneficial genera such as *Faecalibacterium* and *Akkermansia* is linked to metabolic disorders and reduced gut barrier integrity.

One of the most extensively studied microbial biomarkers for gut health is the ratio of Firmicutes to Bacteroidetes (F/B ratio), two dominant bacterial phyla in the human gut microbiota. Together, these phyla typically comprise up to 90% of the bacterial community in healthy individuals. Many Firmicutes are involved in the fermentation of complex carbohydrates, leading to the production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) like butyrate, which play a crucial role in maintaining gut barrier integrity and regulating inflammation. On the other side, Bacteroidetes specialize in breaking down polysaccharides and contribute also to the production of SCFAs, particularly acetate and propionate, which have metabolic and anti-inflammatory effects. Some studies have indicated that obese organisms present a higher F/B ratio than normal-weight individuals and this has been associated as well with type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular disease (Magne et al., 2020).

6.2.3 Towards specific biomarkers of MNP exposure

6.2.3.1 Circulating miRNAs as candidate biomarkers of MNP exposure

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are short, non-coding RNA molecules typically 18–25 nucleotides in length. MiRNAs are coded for in both exons and introns of genes or non-coding RNA transcripts (A. Rodriguez et al., 2004). After processing, mature miRNAs are integrated into the RNA-induced silencing complex (RISC) chiefly consisting of Argonaute Proteins 1–4 (AGO 1–4), Dicer, and TAR RNA-binding protein (TRBP) (Pratt & MacRae, 2009), which guides the RISC to specific mRNA targets, leading to either translational repression or mRNA degradation (Medley et al., 2021).

Freely circulating nucleic acids in the blood were first denoted about 70 years ago (Mandel, 1948). Initially, the scientific community believed that RNA would be unsuitable as a biomarker in blood samples due to the presence of endogenous nucleases presence in plasma (Kamm & Smith, 1972). However, this notion was overturned following miRNA discovery in fixed tissues (Xi et al., 2007). Building on this, a group of miRNAs that were not only present in serum samples but also highly stable were identified (Chen et al., 2008). This pivotal research opened the door to exploring circulating miRNAs as non-invasive biomarkers for several diseases.

In this line, **Plasticheal** made an effort to describe circulating miRNAs that could work as biomarkers of MNPs exposure (Arribas et al., 2024). Validation experiments employing quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) have been conducted to confirm the differential expression of candidate microRNAs (miRNAs) identified through small RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) data obtained from exposed samples of a new cohort of healthy donors, substantiating their potential as circulating biomarkers for plastic exposure (for further details see Deliverable 2.3 of **Plasticheal**).

The subsequent phase should transition to biomonitoring studies aimed at quantifying the expression levels of the identified circulating miRNAs in exposed populations compared to unexposed control groups. From a technical standpoint, this process will necessitate the collection of peripheral blood from donors, followed by plasma separation, miRNA extraction, and quantification via qPCR.

6.2.3.2 Deregulated Gene Expression in white blood cells (WBCs)

Gene expression biomarkers are biological indicators identified through large-scale gene expression studies. Traditionally, research on the transcriptome relied on methods targeting one or a few molecules, such as Northern blotting. However, over the past two decades, significant advancements have been made in technologies enabling large-scale gene expression analysis in specific cells or tissues.

While gene expression biomarkers can be applied to classify any cellular or tissue state, much of the research in this field has focused on pathological conditions, particularly cancer (Vawter & Moon, 2013). In **Plasticheal**, we concentrated on identifying exposure-induced gene expression signatures as predictive biomarkers for MNP exposure.

In general, the discovery and development of gene expression biomarkers typically follow a standardized four-step process (Stransky & de Souza, 2013):

- **Collection of High-Quality Samples:** The process begins with assembling well-characterized and high-quality biological samples to ensure reliable results.
- **Utilization of Large-Scale Gene Expression Platforms:** Advanced technologies are employed to perform comprehensive gene expression analyses across the samples.
- **Biomarker Identification:** Mathematical and computational approaches are used to analyse the data, identifying potential gene expression biomarkers with discriminatory power.
- **Validation:** The identified biomarker's effectiveness and accuracy are confirmed by testing it on an independent set of samples.

Unlike traditional bulk RNA-seq, cutting-edge scRNA-seq techniques enable the identification of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) within individual cells and across diverse cell populations. Insights gained from scRNA-seq analyses hold significant potential for identifying predictive biomarkers. The assessment of gene expression biomarkers from blood samples have been described by Arribas and co-workers (Arribas et al., 2024).

The subsequent phase should transition to biomonitoring studies aimed at quantifying the newly defined gene expression signature in exposed donors, in comparison to unexposed control populations. From a technical perspective, this process will necessitate the collection of peripheral blood from donors, followed by the extraction of white blood cells (WBCs) through red blood cell lysis (or the isolation of peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) via Ficoll density gradient centrifugation), and subsequent quantification using quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR).

6.2.4 Provisional conclusions

Taken together, the findings gathered by the current knowledge on biomarkers, lead to confirm common pathways across the species, as well as similarities in mechanisms of action of MNPs with other foreigner particulates in determining biochemical changes or overt health effects. Indeed, the most common used biomarkers of oxidative stress in literature to MNPs exposure are lipid peroxidation, membrane damage, ROS, SOD, CAT, MDA, GST, GSH, GPx, and TAP. For the inflammatory spectrum, IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, TNF- α , NF-kB and the NLRP3 protein were the most commonly investigated biomarkers. With regard to biomarkers of genotoxicity, MNs, and DNA damage measured by the comet assay were investigated.

The main gap is the lack of human studies. Although some recent investigations have found MNPs in several human samples (Barceló et al., 2023; Huang et al., 2022; Schwabl et al., 2019; Thompson et al., 2024), the meaning and relevance of such findings for human health have still to be elucidated. The presence of foreign particles is a common finding and its relationship with health outcomes has never been clarified. These findings can lead us to propose a minimum set of biomarkers, to be assessed in biological matrices of volunteers and workers with potential exposure to MNPs. This can be further complemented with recently validated biomarkers reflecting long-term endpoints, such as chronic inflammation and fibrosis, as well as cardiovascular endpoints (considering possible interference in the lipid metabolism) (Guseva Canu et al., 2023).

The table in the **Annex 2** summarizes the panel of biomarkers already available and validated in epidemiological studies on nano-objects that also some nano-plastics belong to. In spite of

dissimilarities, the common mode of actions underlying toxic particulates suggest to adopt a similar strategy also for MNPs.

6.2.5 Confounding variables

One important issue regarding biomarkers of early biological effects is the potential influence that confounding factors, related to socio-demographic and lifestyle factors, may have on them. Most effect biomarkers are not specific for one type of exposure. Hence, controlling the potential influence of exogenous or endogenous factors that may affect them is crucial for a correct interpretation of the results. For instance, gender and age are well-known confounding variables affecting the micronucleus (MN) frequency in peripheral blood lymphocytes (MNPBL), with women displaying higher frequencies than men, and a positive correlated age effect (Fenech et al., 2011; Tavares et al., 2022). A significant effect of the country of origin and alcohol consumption on this biomarker was also reported within the HBM4EU project (Tavares et al., 2022). Alcohol consumption also affected the frequency of micronucleated reticulocytes (MNRET), whereas no significant influence on any of the effect biomarkers could be reported regarding smoking habits, which had showed controversial outcomes in previous studies (Fenech et al., 2011; Offer et al., 2005). The observed geographical variability was suggested to be related to i.e., dietary habits, which are expected to have an important influence when assessing the effects of MNP exposure as the presence of plastic particles have been reported in very different types of food and drinks (Ramsperger et al., 2023).

In order to reduce the likelihood of biased result interpretation when associating external exposure with individuals' biomarker levels, potentially confounding variables should be assessed in all volunteers. This will consist in documenting several life habit-, health- and occupational-related factors through answering a detailed questionnaire as described in section 7.5. The corresponding control groups should be chosen to match with the exposed groups at least in terms of country, gender, age and smoking status.

Since EBC collection can be affected by respiratory health status, participants' respiratory function can be assessed using a USB-pneumotachograph by a medical doctor adequately trained for pulmonary function tests (PFTs) as performed in [PlasticsFate](#) project. Before beginning spirometry examination, each participant is asked about his/her medical conditions to ensure that proper precautions may be taken during the test when necessary. Mean Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1), Forced Vital Capacity (FVC) and the Forced Expiratory Fluxes at 25% and 75% of FVC (FEF25–75%) are obtained from the three best acceptable test values of lung function, as recommended by the American Thoracic Society and European Respiratory Society (Stanojevic et al., 2022). A consistent coaching by the person in charge of PFTs will ensure maximum inspiration and forced expiration across tests and participants. Obtained real-time flow volume curves, as well as FVC, FEV1, and FEF25–75% values can be downloaded from respective devices for further post-campaign analysis.

7. FIELD CAMPAIGN PROCEDURES

Following the information visit, a schedule should be planned for the conduction of the field campaigns, in agreement with the company manager and health & safety specialist in the case of workplace studies, or with the health care responsible personnel, when applicable. This field campaigns can follow different schemes, according to the availability of volunteers and the setting (occupational/indoors/general population/vulnerable groups).

The overall campaign can be coordinated using workers' individual registry (i.e., as the electronic registry implemented in the REDCap software (<https://projectredcap.org/software/>)). In the case of occupationally exposed populations, biological sample collection take place in a clean and separate room, to avoid as much as possible sample contamination from air or surface pollutants. When possible, the samples are used for both exposure and effect biomarkers. All procedures described below take place during working hours, and thus are not subject to any compensation or payments given to worker participants. Before, throughout and after the whole campaign, local project leaders should be available to answer questions from workers or company representatives regarding study objectives and procedures.

7.1 Application of ethical permissions

Before initiating any human biomonitoring study, approval from the relevant local Coordinating Ethics Committee is mandatory. No activities related to the study may proceed until ethical permission has been formally granted.

7.2 Information visit procedures

Upon agreement with representatives of companies interested in taking part to the study (manager and/or health & safety specialist) or health care centre personnel, a site information visit is scheduled prior to any worker enrolment. A member from the institution (preferably occupational hygienist, or accompanied by one) conduct this information visit, to avoid as much as possible unnecessary travels and to ease information process in terms of language. This study representative then reports all aspects mentioned below to operational team members in charge of field campaigns.

This information visit serves the following points:

- Ensure a sufficient level of information towards potential worker/volunteer participants, manager and health & safety specialist when applicable, through oral and written explanations regarding the study scope, objectives, procedures, enrolment conditions and potential risks and benefits.
- In the case of occupationally exposed populations, a questionnaire is administered to, or a meeting is scheduled with, the manager or health & safety specialist when applicable, collecting standardized information on company activities, processes at risk for nanoparticle exposure, equipment and infrastructure already available for the protection of their employees.
- Site-specific Health and Safety plan for collaborators is discussed, for future protection of the operational team in charge of field campaigns. This includes asking the company/health care centre representative what types of recognized hazards the facility may contain, which includes physical, chemical, and biological hazards, as well as the types of personal protective equipment required by the facility.
- A walk through the company/ health care centre facilities is performed in order to:
 - Define the scope of activities and workstations to be monitored, including work shift schedules, for both 'Exposed' and 'Internal control' workers (if included).
 - Ensure enough space and document logistical requirements for the use of personal and stationary sampling devices.

- Verify the availability of a room for biological sample collection, including available electrical outlets.
- Informed consent forms including written study information are distributed to workers/volunteers. Time is given to participants for consideration and as an opportunity to ask questions.

The duration of the information visit is estimated to 2 to 3 hours in total, among which 30-45 minutes will be required from workers/volunteers (information about the study, time for consideration and private session to sign the form). Templates of the informed consent form and company questionnaire are available at i.e., [PlasticHeal D10.1](#). The informed consent template should be submitted as part of the ethical permission application.

7.3 Operational team and materials for field campaigns

Field campaigns are conducted by members of an operational team, pre-defined based on a pool of competencies. Whenever possible, the operational team should always include the same collaborators, in order to reduce data collection bias due to inter-experimenter variations. Whenever this is not possible, a person with similar qualifications should be identified and trained to join the team for on-site data collection campaigns. For similar reasons, we try to reduce as much as possible the inter-device variability by using the same device deployment plan for field campaigns, i.e., assignment of a particular device to a specific worker participant for external exposure monitoring and biological sampling.

7.4 Field campaign

7.4.1 Verification of informed consent and identity congruence

Estimated duration: 5 minutes.

No questionnaire administration, external exposure measurement, biological sampling or pulmonary function test should be allowed prior to verification of volunteer's individual written consent, where the different aspects of the data and sample collection and processing are detailed. The participants should agree to the specified terms in order to be included in the study.

7.4.2 Administration of the questionnaire

Estimated duration: 20 minutes.

A questionnaire about their workstation (for workers), their lifestyle habits and medical history in order to control for potential confounding factors is administered to all participants either as a paper document or using tablets with an implemented REDCap software. Participants should have the choice to fill in the questionnaire in English, or in their local (national) language. Operational team members should stay available for questions. The questionnaire is submitted to the local Ethical Committees as part of the ethical permission application after its translation in local languages (if needed). In order to reduce the time granted to workers by the companies to participate in the study, the questionnaire can be provided in advance to the involved workers. In this case, local operational team members should ensure that all the questions have been answered before proceeding with the

sample collection. An example of the detailed questionnaire used in our studies can be found at Deliverable 10.1 of the [PlasticHeal](#) project.

7.4.3 Biological sampling

The following picture (**Figure 1**) summarizes the different biological matrices that have been collected for biomarker determinations by the CUSP projects. The specific matrices and biomarkers assessed in each project are summarized in **Table 2**.

Figure 1. Human samples collected by the different CUSP projects. Maximum amount per sample for EBC, blood and urine, as well as biomarkers of exposure (framed in red) and effects (framed in blue) that have been assessed from the different samples are indicated. *Partly created with BioRender™*

The collection of samples is performed according to the following procedures:

a) Exhaled breath condensate sampling. Estimated duration: 20 minutes.

EBC consists mostly of condensed water vapor from the respiratory tract with small droplets of airway lining fluid from the entire respiratory tract, including bronchial and alveolar regions of the lungs. Within these droplets is an unknown fraction of both volatile and non-volatile substances, as well as particulate materials. Volatile substances are in the form of water-soluble compounds in the condensed water of the EBC sample such as ammonia, hydrogen peroxide and ethanol, while non-volatile substances can include cytokines, lipids and salts, but also environmental and occupational contaminants. An EBC sample is obtained by cooling the exhaled breath bio-aerosol at low temperature. EBC thus represents a useful and non-invasive means of providing important information about the airway lining fluid constituents and lung biopathology.

Exhaled breath condensate samples are collected using a portable condenser (mainly TURBO-DECCS from Medivac, Parma, Italy or – i.e., for **Imptox** - Jaeger Ecoscreen Turbo Disposable Exhaled Condensate Collection System Device, Erich Jager GmbH, Germany). Condensers must

fulfil all recommended practical standards and anti-contamination principles for EBC collection published by the American Thoracic Society and European Respiratory Society (Ahmadzai et al., 2013; Horváth et al., 2017). Volunteers are asked to breathe tidally in the device during 20 minutes through a mouthpiece, while wearing a nose-clip. This mouthpiece is connected to a two-way non-rebreathing valve that traps saliva and allows separation between inspiratory and expiratory air. A condensation temperature of -10 °C is chosen, i.e., as an adequate compromise between volume yield for multiple analyses and detectable concentrations of each compound to be analysed.

As suggested by the European Respiratory Society task force, EBC collection involves a large variable in the volume exhaled for each breath and over time. Thus, EBC collection should consider the volume of exhaled breath, the volume of condensation collected from the exhaled volume and the collection time must be correlated in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the collection of EBC. To achieve this goal, a volume-meter (i.e., VOLMET 20), can be enclosed in line with DECCS circuit, if possible, thus allowing measuring the total volume of air exhaled (i.e., 90 L) during an EBC collection session.

Approximately 0.5-2 mL of EBC can be collected from each participant. Condensing temperatures at the start and end of collection process should be documented, as well as ambient temperature and hygrometry. Given time and concentration requirements and for the sake of participants' compliance, EBC sampling should as much as possible be performed as the last step of all pre-shift samplings.

Upon collection - in glass vials or in PP cryotubes, according to the type of analysis - EBC samples must be frozen as soon as possible in dry ice or at -80 °C temperature for long-term storage. Dry ice boxes are also used for further shipment between laboratories.

b) Urine collection. Estimated duration: 5 minutes.

Urine is a biological fluid representative of the systemic burden supported by an organism. Its collection is logistically easy and non-invasive, making it a useful matrix for the investigation of biomarkers of systemic exposure and morphological or functional effects.

Urine spot samples can be collected once or twice (before starting and after finishing the work shift). A single spot of fresh urine (20 - 50 mL for each participant) is collected in single-use medical grade HDPE urine containers. Each urine container is previously marked twice (side-part and cap) with individuals' specific code-label. As soon as possible after collection, urine is be divided into 1-2 mL-aliquots by an adjustable pipette equipped with disposable tips (the number of aliquots to be prepared for each participant's sample depends on the analyses to be performed). Each aliquot is stored into an Eppendorf tube, appropriately classified with its specific code-label on both the side-part and the cap. All aliquots should be frozen immediately on dry ice, in order to avoid oxidant and antioxidant reactions that could modify their nature before analysis. Additional aliquots of 2-6 ml can be stored in glass vials.

As most sample containers are plastic-made, for MNPs analysis the corresponding polymer types must be reported and considered when performing these analyses.

c) Blood collection Estimated duration: 5-10 minutes.

Blood sampling must only be performed by personnel trained in phlebotomy techniques. In general, blood is collected via venous puncture and handled under sterile conditions. Trained personnel must oversee the procedure and use appropriate personal protective equipment, such as lab coats and gloves. It is essential to keep the blood-handling area clean and free of dust. Only supplies the study's responsible personnel should be used, and talc-free gloves must be worn. The tubes should be prepared and labeled with the code number and other relevant information, such as the date and time of collection. Relevant details, including the time of collection and any unexpected issues, must be recorded on the designated record form.

To prepare for the procedure, the volunteer should be prepped, the garrote placed on the forearm, and the collection site disinfected with 70% alcohol. Approximately 4-8 mL of venous blood per tube is collected by phlebotomy. After loosening the garrote, a cotton ball with 70% alcohol should be pressed against the puncture site. Blood is collected in ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)-, Li/Na-heparin-tubes or in tubes with gel clot activator for serum separation, depending on the type of analyses. Each tube should be gently inverted several times to mix the sample with the anticoagulant and then kept upright until further processing to avoid contact with the stopper. Once the procedure is complete, the volunteer's condition should be checked, and a plaster should be provided for the puncture site as needed.

A total of 12.5 mL (in case of children) or 15-20 mL (in case of adults) of blood can be collected at a single venipuncture procedure.

d) Buccal cells collection Estimated duration: 5-10 minutes

The procedure involves collecting exfoliated oral epithelial cells through a simple, non-invasive method, as previously described (Bolognesi & Fenech, 2019). Samples should be stored at 4°C. If storage at room temperature is unavoidable, it should not exceed three days. When stored at 4°C, samples can remain in the buffer for up to one month.

e) Stool collection Estimated duration: 10 minutes

Stool samples can be collected once or more times in the case of following up studies. In the case of occupationally exposed populations, the collection can be done at home the previous day or during the sample collection day at the workplace by the worker. For that purpose, volunteers are provided with tubes of the OMNIgene®•GUT for Microbiome kit (DNA Genotek Inc.). This kit is designed to collect, stabilize, and store stool samples at room temperature, which simplifies transport and avoids the need for refrigeration. The sample should be taken following the kit's instructions, immediately being sealed the sample in the provided container and stored at room temperature. The stool sample container should be properly labelled with the participant's identification details. Samples can remain at room temperature until transport to the designated location.

Alternatively, samples can be collected using glass with aluminium air tight screw top lids. In this case, samples should be transported in cooler boxes and stored at -20°C until further analysis/processing.

7.5 Sample transportation and storage

Upon the end of the campaign in a particular setting, all samples are transported to the laboratories. If transportation by car is not possible, i.e., the preferred way to keep samples frozen, operational team members in charge of biological samplings can send samples to the laboratories using a courier service for urgent shipments. The delivering service company should guarantee that the integrity of the samples and the required temperature conditions for keeping them are maintained until the shipment reaches the reception laboratory. It is highly recommended to send parcels before Thursday/Friday to ensure reception before the week-end.

Buccal cells, blood and urine samples should be transported refrigerated (at approximately +4 °C), with tubes protected from light in the case of blood. None of these samples must be frozen. EBC samples will be maintained at low temperatures as long as possible by transporting them into dry ice. Stool samples will be kept refrigerated or at room temperature, depending on the collection method.

Upon reception of the shipping box, EBC and urine samples are divided into aliquots if needed, and stored at -20°C for short-term storage (< 30 days) and at -80°C for long-term storage (> 30 days) in laboratory freezers until further analysis.

Blood samples could require different processing before being stored depending on the analyses to be performed. Samples are divided into aliquots and stored at -20°C for the characterization of MNPs. For the analyses of cytokines and miRNAs, blood-EDTA samples are processed to separate the plasma fraction, by centrifuging at 1100×g for 15 min at room temperature. The supernatant (plasma) is immediately aliquoted and transferred in Eppendorf tubes or glass vials –according to the different type of analysis- and stored at -80 °C.

WBCs isolation is performed after plasma collection, then the cell pellet is resuspended in Red Blood Lysis buffer and washed in PBS until a white pellet remained. Cell pellets are immediately processed for single-cell RNA seq or stored at -80°C in 1,5 mL-polypropylene Eppendorf for posterior RNA extraction.

In the case of the comet assay, standard peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs, mostly lymphocytes) isolation (Lymphoprep™) is performed from 2mL of blood from each donor. After isolation, the number of cells is counted using a hemocytometer or an automatic cell counter. Cell samples can be cryopreserved in 500 µL with 90% serum and 10% DMSO (ensure that cells are correctly frozen to be stable during storage) to process later or immediately for DNA breaks measuring (Corredor et al., 2016).

For serum separation, blood is centrifuged at 3000 g for 10 minutes at room temperature. Serum is aliquoted and stored at -80°C until further analysis.

Freezing-and-thawing of the aliquots should be carefully prevented, in order to preserve sterility and avoid repeated thermal shock that could affect the integrity of the biomarkers.

8. SAMPLE ANALYSIS AND DATA PREPROCESSING

The following paragraphs describe the analyses of different human matrices for assessing effect biomarkers. The methods used for characterizing MNPs in human samples have been explained in

section 2.2.1 (Exposure biomarkers). As they are not yet validated, we will not describe them in detail in this report. Nevertheless, deeper descriptions can be found at the corresponding deliverables of each project (i.e., D2.1 and D2.2 in the case of [PlasticHeal](#)).

8.1 Urine samples

Two of the biomarkers of oxidative stress and DNA damage (8-isoprostane and 8-OHdG) are determined by high-sensitivity Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA). This technique is a competitive assay which inversely correlates to analyte concentrations. The corresponding ELISA kit requires 50 μL per sample. After dilution and preparation, samples are read by a multiwall spectrophotometric reader. The limit of detection is 3 pg/mL for 8-isoprostane, and 0.45 ng/mL for 8-OHdG measurements.

The third oxidative stress biomarker (MDA) as well as the total antioxidant capacity (TAC) can be determined by colorimetric assays, which highlight directly and colorimetrically the enzymes or metabolite reactions of antioxidant system or lipid peroxidation. These assays require 10 μL per sample. After dilution and preparation, samples are read by a multiwall spectrophotometric reader. The limit of detection is 44 μM in Trolox equivalents for TAC and 0.0625 μM of TBARS equivalents for MDA measurements.

8.2 EBC samples

Biomarkers of oxidative and nitrosative stress (8-OHdG, nitro-tyrosine), bronchial tract activation, permeability and local inflammation (LTB₄) and vascular inflammation (hs-CRP) can be determined using high-sensitivity ELISA. This technique relies on direct or indirect ELISA and requires 25 μL per sample. Samples are read by a multiwell spectrophotometric reader. The duration ranges from 2 to 5 hours. ELISA / Enzyme Immunoassays (EIA) will also serve for the quantification of 8-isoprostane – ELISA/EIA commercial kits are being analyzed in parallel to assess their sensitivity and reliability. Experimental analytical procedures for the quantification of MDA in EBC are currently undergoing validation and relies on the coupling of Liquid Chromatography with Mass Spectrometry techniques (LC-MS/MS).

Biomarkers of inflammation and immune suppression (TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, IL-10 and IL-17 cytokines) can be determined using Quantum-Pro immunoassay. This technique couples a direct ELISA with Real-Time Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-PCR), in which two antibodies, conjugated with fluorescent RT-PCR probes, are directed against two different epitopes of the same analyte. The RT-PCR reaction signal, proportional to the amount of the analyte, is read by a RT-PCR thermocycler. The assay requires 5 μL per sample, and the duration ranges from 2 to 3 hours.

Surfactant protein D (SP-D) and Krebs von den Lungen 6 (KL-6) glycoprotein can be determined as potential biomarkers of interstitial lung disease by ELISA.

Quantification of particles and MNPs in EBC can be performed as described in section 6.2.1.

8.3 Blood samples

8.3.1 Measurement of biomarkers of inflammation and endothelial dysfunction

Circulating concentrations of PAI-1, IL-6, and endothelial dysfunction biomarkers (sICAM-1 and sVCAM-1) can be determined by enzyme-linked immunoassay (Bioplex, Bio-Rad). CRP and plasma fibrinogen are determined by commercially available kits produced by R&D Systems Inc. (Minneapolis, Minn) and Cusabio (Houston, TX), respectively.

8.3.2 Blood samples for Comet assay

Analysis of mononuclear cells by the comet assay implies that blood samples should be processed as soon as samples arrive to the laboratory, as the protocol involves several critical steps. First, cells are embedded in agarose on a microscope slide or a plastic film, such as GelBond® film. The cells are then lysed using a high-salt and detergent solution, effectively removing cellular components and leaving behind nucleoids containing supercoiled loops of DNA anchored to the nuclear matrix (McArt et al., 2009). Next, the DNA is incubated in an alkaline buffer, which relaxes the strands by allowing those with breaks to unwind and release from their supercoiled state (McArt et al., 2009). During electrophoresis under high-pH conditions, these relaxed DNA strands migrate out of the nucleoid towards the anode, forming structures resembling comets. These structures are subsequently visualized and quantified using fluorescence microscopy. The intensity and length of the comet tail correspond to the extent of DNA damage within the cells (Azqueta et al., 2020; Collins, 2004).

In the **Plasticheal** project, genotoxic damage (DNA strand breaks) and DNA damage (ODD) have been assessed in human populations using the high-throughput Comet assay method. ODD can be assessed by the enzyme-modified comet assay enables the detection of specific types of DNA damage, such as oxidized bases, offering valuable insights into oxidative stress and its genotoxic effects. Specifically, the FPG (formamidopyrimidine-DNA glycosylase)-modified protocol has been employed. This protocol utilizes the enzyme's ability to cleave phosphodiester bonds at sites of oxidized purines in DNA, thereby facilitating the detection of oxidative DNA damage. Hence, genotoxic damage is measured without the addition of enzymes, while ODD is quantified using the FPG enzyme. The assay has been conducted following the standard protocols outlined by Stoyanova and co-workers (Stoyanova et al., 2010), and Singh and co-workers (Singh et al., 1988), with minor modifications. The percentage of DNA in the comet tail is the parameter used to quantify DNA damage, calculated using the Komet 5 software (Kinetics Imaging Ltd).

A detailed protocol is available at D2.3 of the **Plasticheal** project.

8.3.3 Blood samples for MN assays

The analysis of MN by the CBMN assay requires that blood cells should be put in culture as soon as the samples arrive to the laboratory. The protocol of this assay has been previously described in detail (Bolognesi & Fenech, 2019). In the case of the MNRET analysis, as the human spleen sequesters and destroys micronucleated erythrocytes, the analyses should be restricted to the young fraction of micronucleated immature erythrocytes, which can be identified based on the high level of transferrin receptors (CD71+) expressed on their surface (OECD, 2016). However, as the CD71+-labelled population only accounts for approximately the youngest 10–20% of reticulocytes (Dertinger et al.,

2003), an enrichment step is required to ensure an appropriate number of reticulocytes for the analyses (Abramsson-Zetterberg et al. 2000). Therefore, blood samples should be processed within one week after collection. The MNRET assay can be performed according to the protocol adopted by the HBM4EU project (Tavares et al., 2022), which is described in detail in D2.3 of the [PlasticHeal](#) project. A minimum of 20,000 CD71+ cells should be scored (Albertini & Kaden, 2020).

In [PlasticHeal](#), MNRET analyses have been performed using the same blood samples as the ones used for the MN analyses in peripheral lymphocytes. It is worth noting that each biomarker is evaluating different time schedules. MN in long-lived lymphocytes can be assumed to represent genotoxic damage formed during the previous *in vivo* division, and micronucleated cells may accumulate in the cell population due to continuous exposure (Catalán et al., 2006). Hence, the MN PBL assay is a suitable approach for detection of chronic exposure to genotoxins (Nersesyan et al., 2016). Conversely, as the CD71 receptor is lost from the cell surface of the reticulocytes as they mature into erythrocytes, the MNRET assay only reflects an acute genotoxic effect about 3 days before blood sampling (Abramsson-Zetterberg, 2018). On the other hand, the MN PBL detects damage that predominantly has arisen while the lymphocytes are in the peripheral circulation, whereas the MNRET assay detects damage to bone marrow erythroblasts (Abramsson-Zetterberg, 2000).

As mentioned in section 6.2.2.3, micronuclei can also be evaluated from buccal cells following the buccal micronucleus cytome assay (Bolognesi & Fenech, 2019).

8.3.4 Stool samples

Stool samples are used in [PlasticHeal](#) to analyze microbial communities using the MINION sequencer (Oxford Nanopore Technologies) and 16s rRNA gene analysis. This protocol has been successfully implemented in the biomonitoring studies (D2.3 of the [PlasticHeal](#) project). This approach enables a detailed, high-throughput analysis of complex microbiomes, providing valuable data for understanding microbial community structure and its impact on various physiological states.

9. RESULT RESTITUTION TO COMPANIES AND VOLUNTEERS

The results from the exposure and human monitoring campaigns, with results at the group level, are presented to each company. Individual data of exposure biomarkers can be offered to the volunteers of the study. However, data on effect biomarkers cannot only be offered as grouped results. Recommendations and advice are provided to improve practices if required and to improve occupational health and safety policies. These restitutions rely on European regulations, standardization and best practices. The advice should be given with their hierarchical weighting according to the nine prevention principles.

In the [ImpTox](#) project, all participants were informed on the results of their skin prick test, shortly after recruitment. A subgroup of participants (according to their SPT results and personal medical history- self-reported) were invited to the Srebrnjak Children's Hospital for additional diagnostic procedures and tests (additional SPT, allergen-specific IgE in singleplex and multiplex format, lung function tests, oral food challenge test etc.).

Results of the research on exposure and effect biomarkers- at group levels- will be made public, including general public workshops and creation of educational material.

10. CHALLENGES OF PERFORMING HUMAN BIOMONITORING STUDIES WITH MNPs

CUSP projects have identified several common challenges when performing human biomonitoring studies along the last years. The main challenges we have faced are:

- 1) Problems for recruiting companies and volunteers, especially in studies involving occupational settings. As a result, the size of the assessed groups has been smaller than initially planned.
Underrepresentation of either exposed, allergic or control groups due to lack of willingness to participate, or failing to provide certain samples may lead to under- or overrepresentation of some of these groups, and inappropriate interpretation of the results.
- 2) Available volume of sample per collection, especially in the case of EBC and blood samples, which has limited the number of biomarkers that could be assessed from the same sample. Compared to environmental matrices, the smaller available amounts of human matrices may compromise the sensitivity of MNP characterization methods in these samples.
- 3) Plastic contamination during the collection of human samples, which is practically impossible to avoid as most of the devices and materials used are plastic-made.
- 4) Lack of a true “unexposed” population. Although this is a common problem when dealing with environmental contaminants, it leads to the need of larger populations sizes, which is complicated due to the low participation of volunteers
- 5) Need of standardized and high-throughput methods for regulatory biomonitoring. This is urgently need to assess the internal dose of MNPs humans are exposed, as the current available methods have not been yet validated and are time-consuming (manual scoring).

ANNEXES

Annex 1 Statistical analyses and methodology

A1.1 Sample size calculation

Here we report on the sample size calculation for the **AURORA** Household Plastics Study

Sample size can be estimated based on anticipated effect size. Because this study uses a self-controlled longitudinal design, hypothesizing that the usage of less plastic cumulatively reduces MNPs in the human body, Cohen's d is used to quantify anticipated effect size. We expect that there will be significant contrast in MNPs between low and high plastic users. In this study context, M_1 denotes MNPs level at baseline, M_2 denotes MNPs level after three months of follow-up, and SD_{pooled} denotes the pooled standard deviation of MNPs levels at two assessments.

$$\text{Cohen's } d = (M_2 - M_1) / SD_{pooled}$$

Due to a lack of prior knowledge on MNPs, we reference intervention studies on plastic-related chemicals such as bisphenol A (BPA), phthalates, and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), which suggest a concentration reduction of approximately 15% to 60% in urine or blood, with more notable differences found in urine (Chen et al., 2015; Gasiorowski et al., 2022; Rudel et al., 2011). In this study, we will be comparing the low vs high plastic users. We cautiously estimate a difference in MNP concentration between participants of 10% to 50% depending on their plastic use. According to the recent work reporting a mean MNPs concentration of 1.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (SD 2.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) in whole blood from 22 healthy volunteers (Leslie et al., 2022), this corresponds to a mean difference of 0.16 to 0.8 (i.e., the numerator). There have been no human studies evaluating MNPs in urine.

For a pre-post design, Morris (Morris, 2008) suggested to use the standard deviation of the pre-test group. Further, it is recommended to include the correlation between repeated measures for standardization (Lakens, 2013). Assuming a Spearman correlation coefficient of 0.6 (Silver et al., 2021), we obtain a Cohen's d ranging between 0.06-0.3.

Considering budget and practical aspects, we used the maximal effect size anticipated (0.3), a power of 0.8, and a significance level of 0.05 (two-tailed) to calculate the minimal sample size requested, which is 90 (AI-Therapy Statistics Beta, 2022). To account for loss to follow-up, we expand to a total of 110 participants.

Similar studies which evaluated whether changes to food packaging materials or diet resulted in changes in levels of plastic additives and chemicals, including BPA and phthalates, have detected meaningful signals in samples sized as small as 5 and up to 40 (Cirillo et al., 2011; Hutter et al., 2016; Rudel et al., 2011; Sathyanarayana et al., 2013). A recent study in Australian households was sufficiently powered to detect determinants of household dust levels of MNPs with a sample size of 32 (Soltani et al., 2021). Based on these previous studies, we expect that a sample size of 110 will yield meaningful scientific inferences on determinants of internal MNP levels and very novel data on exposure levels in adult females.

A1.2 Statistical analysis plan

First, ‘Exposed’ and ‘control’ groups will be compared using linear models to ensure comparability in terms of demographic and socio-economic variables. Acute effects of occupational exposure to MNPs will be investigated within each group and each campaign using paired t-tests (two-sided) between pre- and post-shift values. Both individuals’ pre-shift values and acute variations (i.e., pre- to post-shift ratio) will be taken into account for subsequent analyses of more chronic effects of occupational exposure to incidental and engineered nanomaterials.

Then, time-series analyses will be conducted to investigate time-dependent variations in particle number concentration (external exposure patterns) with minute-by-minute tasks, production steps, and other events notified in individuals’ logbooks. Time series will be visually inspected for qualitative assessment, then quantitatively described using autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models (Klein Entink et al., 2011). Variations in external exposure patterns (nature and extent) between initial and follow-up field campaigns will be also investigated using linear models accounting for company-specific factors, to evaluate the validity of emission reduction policies.

Finally, multiple regression analysis will be conducted to model the change in each biomarker level occurring along a 4-day exposure, while accounting for individual, environmental and occupational confounding variables collected during field campaigns. Such analyses will be performed first on a within-campaign basis, to associate external exposure patterns and biomarker levels at baseline (i.e., initial field campaign), then to model changes in biomarkers occurring along with the implementation of the exposure control measures over the 6/9-month follow-up by companies. These regression analyses will allow us to validate a set of best-fitting biomarkers to be used in future case-control and medium/long-term prospective cohort studies.

All measurements may be transformed prior to statistical analyses in order to achieve residual normality. Statistical analyses will be performed using a type I error of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$; two-sided tests) with the STATA software, version 16.

AURORA project plans to analyze MNP polymers with a detection rate (i.e., values above the LOD) >40% as continuous variables (i.e., $\mu\text{g/mL}$), and those with a detection rate >20% but <40% as binary variables (i.e., present vs. absent).

A1.3 Handling of missing data

Missing data handling (i.e., with or without imputation) will be determined based on the overall data quality. However, we expect few missing values, given the established rigorous data collection procedures and quality control. A lost-to-follow-up ratio of 20% is estimated, due to constraints related to biological samplings and employee turnover. Only personal data pertaining to participants completing the entire pilot study will be used when comparing initial and follow-up campaigns. Data pertaining to participants having completed the initial, but not the follow-up campaign, will still enter statistical analyses aiming at evaluating within-campaign (baseline) exposure time series, and associations between external exposure patterns and biomarker levels.

AURORA project imputed missing MNP concentrations (including values below the LODs) using maximum likelihood estimation, conditional on a normal distribution of (natural) log-transformed values. We did not impute concentrations of MNP polymers with a detection rate <40%.

Annex 2 Panel of biomarkers already available and validated in epidemiological studies on nano-objects

<i>Biomarker</i>	<i>Biological matrix</i>	<i>Physiological/Pathological meaning</i>
8-isoprostane	Urine/EBC	Oxidative stress
Malondialdehyde (MDA)	Urine/EBC/blood	Oxidative stress – lipid peroxidation
8-Oxo-2'-deoxyguanosine (8OHdG)	Urine/EBC	DNA oxidative damage
Total Antioxidant Power (TAP)	Urine	Antioxidant capacity
Particle size and number concentration	EBC	Estimation of particle deposited dose (lung)
Tumor necrosis factor (TNF- α)	EBC	Pro-inflammatory cytokine
Interleukin 1 beta (IL-1 β)	EBC	Pro-inflammatory cytokine
Interleukin 6 (IL-6)	EBC	Pro-inflammatory cytokine
Interleukin 10 (IL-10)	EBC	Immuno-suppressive cytokine
Leukotriene B4 (LTB4)	EBC	Bronchial tract activation, permeability and local inflammation
C-Reactive Protein (Hs-CRP)	EBC	Low grade systemic inflammation
Krebs von den Lungen glycoprotein 6 (KL-6)	EBC	interstitial lung disease; activation of pro-fibrotic cascade
Gpx1: glutathione peroxidase; SOD: superoxide dismutase	Blood /plasma	Antioxidant enzyme activity: Antioxidant capacity
Intercellular adhesion molecule (ICAM-1); Vascular adhesion molecules (VCAM-1); plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 (PAI-1)	Blood	Vascular endothelial activation; activation of prothrombotic cascade
DNA strand breaks (Comet assay + FPG-ENDO III)	Blood	Basal and oxidatively damaged DNA
Chromosome damage (Micronucleus assay)	Blood Buccal cells	Basal chromosome damage
DNA (hypo/hyper)methylation microRNA (miRNAs)	Blood	Impaired expression of genes involved in DNA methylation reactions leading to global DNA methylation changes; gene-specific methylation of tumour suppressor, inflammatory, and DNA repair genes; potential cancer development. DNA hypermethylation might represent biomarker of both exposure and disease development (i.e., fibrosis, cancer).

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